

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges

Deliverable D8.2

Deliverable: D8.2 EOSC service model

31/12/2020

Abstract. NEANIAS develops thematic services for EOSC communities on the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The project will integrate the thematic services into the EOSC ecosystem after they reach the maturity required by EOSC. This deliverable presents the service management system that will guide the design, development and delivery of NEANIAS services, such that all services are properly modelled, evolved and represented according to the service description template, provided by the catalogue of the EOSC Portal. In addition, it provides the descriptions of the services which populate the NEANIAS service catalogue.

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Glossary/ Definitions

The NEANIAS service management system uses the following terms (adopted from FitSM):

Term	Definition
Incident	Unplanned disruption of operation in a service or service component, or degradation of service quality versus the expected or agreed service level or operational level according to service level agreements (SLAs), operational level agreements (OLAs) and underpinning agreements (UAs).
IT service	Service that is enabled by the use of information technology (IT)
IT service management (ITSM)	Entirety of activities performed by an IT service provider to plan, deliver, operate and control IT services offered to customers
Key performance indicator (KPI)	Metric that is used to track the performance, effectiveness or efficiency of a service or process
Management system	Entirety of policies, processes, procedures and related resources and capabilities aiming at effectively performing management tasks in a given context and for a given subject
Operational level agreement (OLA)	Agreement between a service provider or federation member and another part of the service provider's organisation or the federation to provide a service component or subsidiary service needed to allow the provision of services to customers.
Policy	Documented set of intentions, expectations, goals, rules and requirements, often formally expressed by top management representatives in an organisation or federation
Procedure	Specified set of steps or instructions to be carried out by an individual or group to perform one or more activities of a process
Process	Structured set of activities, with clearly defined responsibilities, that bring about a specific objective or set of results from a set of defined inputs
Release	Set of one or more changes to configuration items (CIs) that are grouped together and deployed as a logical unit
Service	Way to provide value to customers through bringing about results that they want to achieve
Service catalogue	Customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about these services

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Term	Definition
Service level agreement (SLA)	The documented agreement between a customer and service provider that specifies the service to be provided and the service targets that define how it will be provided.
Service management	Entirety of activities performed by a service provider to plan, deliver, operate and control services offered to customers
Service management plan	Overall plan for implementing and operating a service management system (SMS)
Service management system (SMS)	Overall management system that controls and supports management of services within an organisation or federation
Service portfolio	Internal list that details all the services offered by a service provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued
Service provider	Organisation or federation (or part of an organisation or federation) that manages and delivers a service or services to customers
Service request	User request for information, advice, access to a service or a pre-approved change
Underpinning agreement (UA)	Documented agreement between a service provider and an external supplier that specifies the underpinning service(s) or service component(s) to be provided by the supplier, and the service targets that define how it will be provided.

1. Introduction

The NEANIAS EU project aims to develop and integrate services to EOSC in the field of Underwater, Atmospheric and Space research. The objective is to share these thematic services with scientific researchers of EOSC communities on these fields.

This deliverable aims to introduce the NEANIAS service management system, i.e. the set of policies, objectives, processes, procedures and tools, etc., which will support the design, development and delivery of NEANIAS services. The establishment of the NEANIAS service management system will ensure that the entire lifecycle of NEANIAS services is governed by specific rules, which in turn will ensure that the services are developed and operated in a consistent manner. Apart from the service management system, this deliverable also presents the NEANIAS service model, which adopts and extends when needed the latest EOSC service model, called EOSC Profiles (v3.0)¹. The use of the EOSC model and its basic concepts as the basis for modelling the NEANIAS service providers and service descriptions covers the modelling needs of NEANIAS service providers and aims to facilitate the on-boarding of the NEANIAS services to EOSC.

The structure of this document is as follows: Section 2 presents background information about the establishment of the NEANIAS service management system, and the standards and practices it is based on. In Section 3, the scope of the NEANIAS service management system is presented. Sections 4, 5 and 6 describe the policy, objectives and plan of the NEANIAS service management system, respectively. Section 7 presents the processes and procedures that comprise the NEANIAS service management system. Section 8 focuses on the service model adopted by NEANIAS, and describes NEANIAS services based on this model. In Section 9, key assumptions and considerations for the implementation of the NEANIAS service management system are presented. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section 10.

¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation>

2. Background information about the establishment of NEANIAS service management system

2.1. Rationale for service management framework selection

Before establishing the service management system of NEANIAS, it is important to select the basis (i.e., framework or standard) that will guide its development. For this purpose, the following standards, frameworks and practices in the area of IT Service Management are examined:

- ISO/IEC 20000:2018 [1]
- FitSM [2]
- IT Infrastructure Library (ITIL) [3]

In general, the implementation of a service management system (SMS) consists of 4 different levels:

1. The standard or framework that provides the fundamental principles for the structure and the contents of the SMS and its operation;
2. The standard or framework that provides more detailed guidelines for the design and development of the SMS;
3. A set of (good) practices providing detailed guidance on the design of SMS processes and procedures;
4. A set of policies, processes, procedures and other SMS artefacts, which are developed based on the principles and guidelines of the above three levels.

The above hierarchy is depicted on the following Figure, which also shows the positioning of ISO 20000, FitSM and ITIL in the IT Service Management area:

Figure 1: IT Service Management Framework overview

2.1.1. ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018

The ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 specifies requirements for an organization to establish, implement, maintain and continually improve a service management system (SMS). The requirements specified in this standard include the planning, design, transition, delivery and improvement of services to meet the service requirements and deliver value. The structure of an SMS based on ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 is shown on Figure 2².

Figure 2: ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 structure

ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 is an international standard sponsored by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and is currently considered the No.1 standard in the industry for the development of service management frameworks. It is an entire family of documents, comprising more than ten (10) documents/ parts, each one providing guidance in specific areas. Moreover, it is certifiable and well-aligned with other standards and frameworks, such as ISO 9000, 27000, 31000, ITIL, COBIT, etc.

2.1.2. FitSM

FitSM³ is a free and lightweight standards family aimed at enabling effective IT service management in the broadest range of organisations. FitSM is well-established in the Research & Academic domains. The following figure shows a possible grouping of the FitSM processes, based on six main topic areas.

² Source: ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018

³ Source: FitSM, Part 0: Overview and vocabulary, <https://www.fitsm.eu/downloads/>

Figure 3: FitSM contents

The main advantage of FitSM is that the development of an IT SMS based on it requires less effort compared to the ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018. On the other hand, no certification is available for SMS developed based on FitSM.

2.1.3. IT Infrastructure Library

IT Infrastructure Library (or ITIL) is the most widely recognized framework for IT and digitally enabled services in the world⁴. ITIL is not a standard, rather it is considered as best practice for the design and development of an effective service management system.

ITIL provides guidance to organizations and individuals on how to use IT as a tool to facilitate business change, transformation and growth. It emphasizes on the alignment of IT with business strategies, objectives and goals.

ITIL was recently (in 2019) updated to version 4 (ITIL 4) in order to accommodate current technology and needs, also recognizing IT as an integral part of the business and, at the same time, as an enabler for the business to achieve its goals.

ITIL sees service management from four different perspectives (“dimensions”):

⁴ <https://www.axelos.com/best-practice-solutions/itil>

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Figure 4: The four dimensions of service management

ITIL 4 also provides a holistic framework for best-practice IT service management. It introduces the service value system (SVS) to represent how different components and activities of the organization work together to facilitate value creation through IT-enabled services⁵.

Figure 5: The ITIL service value system

ITIL guidance is organized around “management practices”, which fall into 3 categories; general, service management, and technical management. In this respect it addresses all

⁵ Introductory Overview of ITIL 4, https://www.tsoshop.co.uk/gempdf/Introductory_Overview_of_ITIL4.pdf

topics and requirements of ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018, however with (minor) differences in the grouping of service management processes.

2.1.4. Adoption of service management framework for NEANIAS

For the selection of the most appropriate service management framework for the development of the NEANIAS SMS, the following considerations were taken into account:

- Certification or full compliance with a specific ITSM standard/ framework is not within the scope of the project.
- Whichever ITSM standard/ framework is selected, several adjustments/ adaptations will be made for NEANIAS project (and services) purposes.
- There is a quite good alignment between the FitSM processes and the ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 corresponding ones.
- ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 is more complete, but also more demanding than FitSM.
- EOSC-hub manages its Hub portfolio with FitSM and we expect FitSM to be used in the EOSC Core from 2021.

Based on the above, it was decided that focus should be given on the ITSM processes to be developed and their adjustments to the NEANIAS project, and not to the strict conformance to a specific ITSM framework. For this purpose, it was decided that *FitSM be used as the basis for the NEANIAS SMS* with ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018 extensions (where/if needed), utilising also ITIL guidance as best practice.

2.2. Development approach

EOSC integration plan [4] suggests the use of an agile approach based on successive development cycles for achieving the following objectives:

- Publish NEANIAS thematic services in EOSC. Consider the publishing of additional NEANIAS services in EOSC in a future stage.
- Integrate NEANIAS services (thematic and core) with relevant EOSC services where we see value of the integration. (e.g. to enhance our operations, to deliver more features to users)
- Develop the NEANIAS IT Service Management System gradually, and in an EOSC compatible way.

Inevitably, the NEANIAS service management system shall enable the achievement of the objectives set in the EOSC integration plan, also following a similar agile approach for its development.

Initially the foundations of the NEANIAS service management system shall be defined, i.e.:

- The **scope** of the NEANIAS service management system,
- The service management **policy**,
- The service management **objectives** and
- The service management **plan**.

Then, the key **service management processes** that will enable the design and operation of NEANIAS services shall be defined. The processes (and supporting procedures) to be defined need to focus on the visibility of the services, the interaction of NEANIAS, as service provider, with its customers (users of the NEANIAS services) as well as on areas related to the enhancement/ improvement and troubleshooting of the services.

Figure 6: The building blocks of the NEANIAS Service Management System

The foundations and the initial set of processes of the NEANIAS service management system are presented in this deliverable. Last but not least, as the NEANIAS service releases mature over time, the NEANIAS service management system may also need to be adjusted or extended with additional processes in order to facilitate future needs.

3. Service management scope

For defining the scope of the NEANIAS service management system, it is important to understand the relationship between NEANIAS, as the overall provider of services to EOSC and the Research Communities, and the providers of the thematic and core services developed within the NEANIAS project. As the providers of the thematic and core services belong to the NEANIAS ecosystem, they are considered as “internal” suppliers of NEANIAS, providing services or service components, which in turn are delivered by NEANIAS to its “customers”.

Figure 7: The NEANIAS service provisioning ecosystem

Having this in mind, together with the type of services delivered as well as the target user groups, the scope of the NEANIAS service management system is defined as follows:

The scope of the Service Management System of NEANIAS are the services provided by the NEANIAS project consortium according to the project DoA

Figure 8: Scope of the NEANIAS service management system

4. Service management policy

NEANIAS has defined the following policy regarding the design, delivery, monitoring and continuous improvement of its services. All partners of NEANIAS declare their support for this policy. A copy of this policy will be published on the NEANIAS website.

NEANIAS is committed to promote Open Science practices and contribute to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of EOSC, through the design and delivery of Sustainable Innovative Underwater, Atmospheric and Space Research Services.

NEANIAS aims to enhance **innovation** both at the technology and business level:

(a) **technological innovation**: enhancing service capabilities by adding capacities and resources via EOSC Hub⁶ and RI services integration; introducing new data flows stemming from the ability to consume and generate data under FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles; delivering to operational usage new functionalities; introducing new collaboration models for researchers using the instruments of established EOSC Hub services.

(b) **business innovation**: identifying new solutions to challenges in delivering value chains in the Open Science and EOSC/EOSC Hub environment; identifying new stakeholder roles both as consumers and providers of resources, be it physical, virtual, or human ones.

NEANIAS aims to address **sustainability** via:

(a) innovation and quality: delivering high-quality innovative services that can establish a loyal user base and can trigger demand.

(b) flexibility / expandability / reusability: delivering services that can be adapted to accommodate new use cases, designed under a top-down/bottom-up approach that abstracts over specific challenges, towards generalization and re-focuses on specific cases, while maintaining flexibility, addressing cases beyond the initially defined ones.

(c) agility: applying (i) a sustainability methodology that provides essential feedback to technological and strategic guidance activities of the project and (ii) an agile development methodology that captures user feedback early in the implementation lifecycle.

(d) promotion: promoting services into becoming poles of attraction for new users and research groups, beyond their initial frame of application.

(e) economic viability: ensuring viable business models around services that in turn are economic with respect to the use of resources (efficiency), flexible to embrace new needs, and scalable to support an expanding user base.

NEANIAS services are designed, operated, and monitored under a service management system that adheres to standards and adopts well-established practices and tools. NEANIAS partners are constantly seeking opportunities for the improvement and enhancement of the services, taking into account the needs of the services' consumers as well as incidents and issues arising during service provisioning.

⁶ The EOSC-hub project that operates 'EOSC Hub' is coming to an end in 2021. We expect a change of terminology afterwards to 'EOSC-Core', as used in the 'Solutions for a sustainable EOSC' report by the EOSC Sustainability WG.

5. Service management objectives

The objectives of the NEANIAS service management system are aligned with the overall objectives of the NEANIAS project. These objectives are to:

- Ensure quality of services while continually looking for improvement opportunities
- Align the use of cutting-edge technology with the needs and capabilities of service users
- Enable access to innovative services
- Leverage the risks of service delivery through operational efficiency

6. Service management plan

6.1. List of services

The services within the scope of the NEANIAS service management system are of two types:

1. **Thematic services**, i.e. services in specific scientific sectors; Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research
2. **Core services**, i.e. innovative reusable services that can be used outside the context of their initial implementation scope, such as Data sharing, EOSC/RIs Integration services, Artificial Intelligence (AI) services, and Visualisation services.

The list of NEANIAS services, as compiled at the time of writing this deliverable, is shown in the following tables. The purpose and technical characteristics of each service are described in Deliverables D2.3/4, D3.3/4, D4.3/4 and D6.3.

Table 1: List of NEANIAS thematic services

Short name	Sector	Lead
UW-BAT	Underwater	TELEDYNE
UW-MOS	Underwater	CORONIS
UW-MAP	Underwater	ATHENA
Atmo-FLUD	Atmospheric (A1)	ATHENA
Atmo-Stress	Atmospheric (A2)	UNIMIB
Atmo-Seism	Atmospheric (A2)	UNIMIB
Atmo-4CAST	Atmospheric (A3)	UBIWHERE
SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service	SPACE-VIS (S1)	INAF
SPACE-VIS ADN Service	SPACE-VIS (S1)	ALTEC
ADAM-SPACE	SPACE-VIS (S1)	JACOBS/ MEE0
ADAM-DPS	SPACE-MOS (S2)	MEE0/ JACOBS
SPACE-ML CAESAR service	SPACE-ML (S3)	INAF
SPACE-ML AstroML service	SPACE-ML (S3)	INAF

Table 2: List of NEANIAS core services

Short name	Sector	Lead
Catalogue Service	C1	ATHENA
DVS	C1	NKUA
NEANIAS Web Toolkit	C1	CITE
Catalogue Portal (C1.1)	C1	ATHENA
NEANIAS AAI	C2	CITE
Configuration Service	C2	CITE
Service Instance Registry	C2	CITE
Logging	C2	CITE
Accounting	C2	CITE
Notifications	C2	CITE
Data Depositing service	C2	GARR
Data Sharing	C2	NKUA
Data Transfer	C2	SZTAKI
Data Exploration	C2	MEEO
GARR Cloud Platform Service	C2	GARR
GARR Container Platform	C2	GARR
GARR DaaS	C2	GARR
MiCADO	C2	SZTAKI
C3.1-AI-Gateway	C3	SZTAKI
C3.2-Model-Serving	C3	ALTEC
C3.3-Horovod-Cluster	C3	SZTAKI
C3.4-Spark-Cluster	C3	UNIMIB
VD-VisIVO	C4	INAF
VD-Splotch	C4	UoP
VD-Maps	C4	CORONIS
C4.2- Visualization Gateway	C4	INAF
C4.3- Toolkit for Cross Realities - PMS	C4	ALTEC
C4.3- Toolkit for Cross Realities - DCS	C4	ALTEC
C4.4-Spatial Data Stores	C4	JACOBS

6.2. Authorities and responsibilities

The main roles involved in the design, operation and monitoring of the processes of the NEANIAS service management system are shown in the following table:

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process

Additionally to the above, for each service management process, other roles, specific to this process, are defined.

6.3. Technology

The effectiveness and efficiency of the NEANIAS service management system, in its entirety or specific components thereof, are highly dependent of the technological solutions that support the execution of the processes and procedures. The main tools that support the NEANIAS SMS include the following:

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to service providers to register and describe their services • Presents information about the services that NEANIAS provides to users • Enables service ordering • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents and service requests, complaints, requirements about services, etc.
NEANIAS ticketing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of incidents and service requests, complaints, changes, etc.
NEANIAS wiki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system

The above tools are complemented by own tools of the thematic/core service providers, which focus on the more technical aspects of service management (e.g. performance monitoring, logging, event management, capacity management etc.).

6.4. Performance evaluation & Continual improvement

The NEANIAS Service Management System and the NEANIAS services are not static in nature; they are under constant monitoring and improvement so that they adjust to the needs of the customers/ users of the services and the ever-changing technical environment that support the delivery of the services. Moreover, as a management system, the NEANIAS SMS processes and procedures need a short period of time in order to mature and enhance their effectiveness and efficiency.

Towards the evaluation of the performance and the continual improvement of the NEANIAS SMS and the services, the NEANIAS consortium has taken the following main measures:

At the operational level, a number of service management processes, which support such activities, have been established. First, through the Continual Service Improvement Management process, nonconformities and deficiencies related to the IT Service Management Framework as well as deficiencies in the performance of services are identified, prioritised, and addressed. Opportunities for improvement are exploited with the use of the same process as well. Second, through the Service Reporting Management process, reporting about the performance of the services is enabled, thus allowing to easily compare target levels of service with the actual ones achieved. A number of supplementary service management processes, although they have different goals, also provide inputs to performance evaluation and continual improvement, e.g. Customer Relationship Management and Service Level

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Management. Finally, for each service management processes, one or more Key Performance Indicators have been defined.

At the technical level, the performance of the services is monitored and measured by own tools of the service providers. Deficiencies identified are then addressed, through the service management processes, again by the toolset available at each service provider. At the NEANIAS level, the NEANIAS catalogue portal assists in gathering input for performance evaluation and continual improvement, as it allows service users to submit incidents and service requests, as well as complaints about the services, which may lead to changes that improve the delivery of the services. Moreover, it enables the execution of customer satisfaction surveys.

7. Service management processes

For the initial establishment of the NEANIAS service management system, as described in section 2.2, 8 out of the 14 processes of the FitSM framework have been adopted. These processes, which focus on the visibility of the services, the interaction of NEANIAS with the users of its services) as well as on areas related to the enhancement/ improvement and troubleshooting of the services, are:

Table 3: NEANIAS service management processes

Process ID	Process title
SPM	Service portfolio management
SLM	Service level management
SRM	Service reporting management
CRM	Customer relationship management
ISRM	Incident and service request management
CHM	Change management
RDM	Release and deployment management
CSI	Continual service improvement management

The adoption of the remaining 6 processes of the FitSM framework by NEANIAS will be reconsidered in the future as service releases and the service management system itself mature, and new needs, which cannot be facilitated by the initial set of service management processes, arise.

The above service management processes are supported by the following procedures:

Table 4: NEANIAS service management procedures

Procedure ID	Procedure title
CRM1	Handling customer complaints
CRM2	Reviewing customer satisfaction
ISRM1	Handling Incidents & Service Requests
CHM1	Handling Changes

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Procedure ID	Procedure title
RDM1	Building and Deploying Releases
CSI1	Handling Improvements

The service management processes and procedures of the NEANIAS Service Management System are presented in Annex A of this deliverable.

8. Service model

The service model within the service management system aims to offer to all NEANIAS service providers a uniform way of describing their services within their service portfolio. It captures in the form of metadata the main characteristics of the lifecycle of a service, including the ones that will be made publicly available through the NEANIAS catalogue of services.

One of the main project objectives is to design and deliver services which will be onboarded on EOSC. Thus, the description of the NEANIAS services took into account the recently published (i.e., mid-November 2020) latest version of the onboarding process for Providers and the new Service model of EOSC⁷ (i.e., EOSC Provider Profiles and EOSC Resource profiles). EOSC Profiles consider two main concepts; the Organization which acts as a provider of a resource and the resources provided by this organization to be findable, orderable and accessible in EOSC ecosystem. NEANIAS reuses the proposed modelling concepts, such that NEANIAS Service providers are modelled based on the EOSC provider profiles and NEANIAS Services are modelled based on the EOSC resource profiles. This choice aims to facilitate the onboarding of NEANIAS providers and services in the EOSC catalogue, complying with the existing standards and EOSC guidelines.

The provider model organizes information about a service provider in the following building blocks:

- **Basic Information:** basic information about a provider such as the unique provider identifier in the catalogue, the name, the abbreviation, the Provider website, etc.
- **Marketing Information:** the description, the logo and multimedia on the Provider if available.
- **Classification Information:** information about the classification of the provider, such as scientific domain and subdomain, and tags.
- **Location Information:** information about the location of the Provider.
- **Contact Information:** information about the contact persons of the Provider.
- **Maturity Information:** information about the maturity of the Provider (Life Cycle status and Certifications).
- **Other Information:** other information related to the Provider and its activity.

The Service model organizes information in the following categories:

- **Basic Information:** ID, Name, Resource Organisation, Resource Providers, Webpage
- **Marketing Information:** Description, Tagline, Logo, Multimedia, Use Cases
- **Classification Information:** Scientific Domain and Subdomain, Category and Subcategory, Target Users, Access Type and Mode, Tags
- **Geographical and Language Availability Information**
- **Resource Location Information:** information about the Geographic Location a service is hosted or deployed (including the data processed by the service).
- **Contact Information for:**

⁷ <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation>

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- Main Contact/Resource Owner and Public Contact: Name, Email, Phone, Position, Organisation
 - Other Contacts: Helpdesk Email, Security Contact Email
- **Maturity Information:** Technology Readiness Level, Life Cycle Status, Certifications, Standards, Open Source Technologies, Version, Last Update, Change Log
- **Dependencies Information:** Required Resources, Related Resources, Related Platforms
- **Attribution Information:** Funding Body, Funding Program, Grant/Project Name
- **Management Information**
 - Helpdesk Page
 - User Manual
 - Terms Of Use
 - Privacy Policy
 - Access Policy
 - Service Level
 - Training Information
 - Status Monitoring
 - Maintenance
- **Access and Order Information:** Order Type, Order
- **Financial Information:** Payment Model, Pricing

The completion of some of the above fields is mandatory, while for some others is optional. Moreover, the values to fill-in in some of the fields come from controlled vocabularies.

The detailed description of the NEANIAS services based on the EOSC Profiles are presented in Annex B of this deliverable.

It should be noted that one of the tasks on the service modelling is to gather feedback by NEANIAS service providers which concern changes either in the attributes of the EOSC model (e.g., addition of a new type of information, change of an existing attribute from mandatory to optional, etc.) or changes in the accepted values used in the controlled vocabularies. Such changes will be gathered and reviewed by WP8, in order to

- a) Extend the NEANIAS service model underlying the service portfolio management and the NEANIAS service catalogue
- b) Be communicated as model change requests to the EOSC onboarding team.

On the opposite direction, new versions of the EOSC model, will be reviewed and when appropriate adopted by the NEANIAS service model, especially those that require the adaptation of the model for the onboarding / update of services in the EOSC catalogue.

Potential changes to the NEANIAS service model, originating either by NEANIAS service providers (asking for changes/ extensions to the service model) or by EOSC (updating the service model or the onboarding process) will be accommodated through existing processes of the NEANIAS service management system, e.g. the Continual Service Improvement Management process (for improvement requests originating from NEANIAS service providers), the Customer Relationship Management process (for changes/ requirements

coming from EOSC) and the Change Management Process (which enables the implementation of the changes).

9. Service management implementation

After the service management system of NEANIAS has been established, and the NEANIAS services have been documented in a compatible way to EOSC requirements, the next step is to proceed with the implementation of the SMS within the lifecycle of the NEANIAS services as well as develop/ adjust the project tools to support it. Finally, NEANIAS services shall be, gradually, onboarded on EOSC.

Adoption of NEANIAS service management processes and procedures by thematic/core service providers

In the short-term the providers of NEANIAS services will need to review the SMS processes and procedures and integrate them at the currently employed practices for service design and operation. This may yield the need for changes in current practices, which in the short-term may require some additional effort, however in the mid and long term it will enhance the user focus, will improve the effectiveness and efficiency in service delivery and enable the project achieve a certain level of homogeneity in service delivery. Another possible outcome from this approach is the identification of improvement opportunities for the NEANIAS service management system itself. These improvement opportunities are always welcome and contribute to the continual improvement of the SMS. Moreover, combined with other factors (e.g. technology), they raise the maturity level of the SMS and the services.

Development and configuration of tools

The second, but equally important, category of actions for the implementation of service management in NEANIAS project refers to the development and configuration of IT tools that will support the automation of service management processes and procedures. The main tools to be used for the IT-enablement of NEANIAS SMS are described both in the NEANIAS Service Management Plan (section 6.3) and at the descriptions of the SMS processes in Annex A. It should be noted that the list of tools as well as their exact details about their functionality and behaviour within the NEANIAS SMS will be revisited and finalised during the initial stages of the service management implementation.

Onboarding NEANIAS services on EOSC

Based on the NEANIAS service models presented in this deliverable, onboarding of the services to EOSC need to be initiated, following the maturity level of each service. According to the DoA of the project, at least nine (9) thematic services will be onboarded to EOSC. Prior to EOSC onboarding, the population of NEANIAS service catalogue will be done.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable discussed two main topics:

1. the establishment of the NEANIAS service management system and
2. the description of the NEANIAS services following a common, EOSC-compliant profile.

For the NEANIAS service management system, initially the rationale behind its development was presented, i.e. which service management standard or framework would be used as the basis for its development. Then the approach for the development of the service management system was presented, highlighting the main building blocks of the system, i.e. the service management scope, policy, objectives, plan and processes. These building blocks were further elaborated in the deliverable, resulting in the establishment of the NEANIAS service management system, which will govern the entire lifecycle of NEANIAS services, from planning and design to delivery and operation, until their retirement (if/where applicable).

For the second main topic of the deliverable, i.e. the description of the NEANIAS services, we took into account the objectives and the context of the NEANIAS project. Therefore, the EOSC requirements and guidelines for service modelling were adopted by the project in order to facilitate the future onboarding of NEANIAS services to EOSC. Both thematic and core services developed in the context of NEANIAS were modelled according to the EOSC model. Information about NEANIAS service providers were also completed using the EOSC corresponding model (i.e. the provider profile).

Finally, the integration of service management practices, as described in the NEANIAS service management system, was discussed. To this end, the main categories of actions related to the service management implementation are:

- Adoption of NEANIAS service management processes and procedures by thematic/core service providers. Towards this goal, we will:
 - assist service providers in integrating the service management processes and procedures in the practices they already use for service delivery
 - seek for opportunities for improving the NEANIAS service management processes and procedures, which may arise during this process
- Development and configuration of tools that will support the automation of service management processes and procedures. For this purpose, we will:
 - work with WP7 in order to finalise the NEANIAS toolset and the requirements of each tool
 - be monitoring the development of the tools, in order a) to ensure conformance with the NEANIAS service management system, and b) to identify improvement opportunities in the NEANIAS service management processes and procedures.
- Onboarding NEANIAS services on EOSC following the maturity level of each service. Towards this goal, we will assist service providers:
 - During the registration of their services on the NEANIAS catalogue
 - During the EOSC onboarding process

References

- [1] ISO/IEC 20000-1:2018, Information technology — Service management — Part 1: Service management system requirements, [<https://www.iso.org/standard/70636.html>]
- [2] FitSM Standards for lightweight IT service management [<https://www.fitsm.eu/>]
- [3] IT Infrastructure Library [<https://www.axelos.com/best-practice-solutions/itil>]
- [4] NEANIAS project, Deliverable D8.1: EOSC integration plan

Annex A: NEANIAS service management processes and procedures

A1: NEANIAS service management processes

Service Portfolio Management

1. Document control

Process ID	SPM
Process title	Service Portfolio Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to define and maintain the NEANIAS Service Portfolio. The NEANIAS Service Portfolio is a database that details all the services offered by NEANIAS, including those in preparation, live and discontinued, as well as those meant to serve EOSC users and those that are internal for the project. The service portfolio is the basis of the NEANIAS service catalogue, which will be shared with the customers (i.e. the catalogue is the public-face of the portfolio and is visible on the NEANIAS website and the EOSC Portal).

The service portfolio shall be maintained during the whole project and all services shall be specified as part of the service portfolio. The design and the release process of a new or changed service should be planned and these plans shall consider the timescales, responsibilities, new or changed technology, communication and service acceptance criteria. Finally, the organizational structure that will support the delivery methods should be identified as well. The defined service portfolio should be maintained during the long-term sustainability period after the end of the project.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Define the NEANIAS Service Portfolio
- Maintain the NEANIAS Service Portfolio (updates, publishing to EOSC, retirements)

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
SPM1	A service portfolio shall be maintained. All services shall be specified as part of the service portfolio.	

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SPM2	Design and transition of new or changed services shall be planned.	
SPM3	Plans for the design and transition of new or changed services shall consider timescales, responsibilities, new or changed technology, communication and service acceptance criteria.	
SPM4	The organisational structure supporting the delivery of services shall be identified, including a potential federation structure as well as contact points for all parties involved.	

4. Role model

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process
Service owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as the primary contact point for all (process-independent) concerns in the context of that specific service To maintain the description of a specific entry in the service portfolio Act as an “expert” for the service in technical and non-technical concerns Maintain the service documentation, such as the service specification / description To gather and analyse customer feedback about the service To plan service development, to prepare development roadmap To roll out new and validated service versions into the live environment

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Specification of NEANIAS service portfolio (from NEANIAS project workplan)
- Details about NEANIAS services (from service owners)
- Customer demands and requirements (from CRM)

5.2.Activities

- Update the NEANIAS service portfolio
- Review the NEANIAS service portfolio

5.3.Key outputs

- NEANIAS service portfolio
- Availability of NEANIAS services for EOSC users

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system

NEANIAS catalogue portal	Provides the interface to service providers to register and describe their services
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6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: “require from” or “provide to”	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Customer Relationship Management	Customer demands and requirements
Provide to	Service Level Management	Service portfolio updates, incl. trigger to register or update a NEANIAS service in EOSC

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Number of thematic service entries in the NEANIAS Service Portfolio	9 (Section 1.4.1 of DoA): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 underwater: Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data, Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data, Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data 3 atmospheric: Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring, Atmospheric Perturbations and Components Monitoring, Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting 3 space: FAIR Data Management and Visualization, Map Making and Mosaicing of Multidimensional Space Images, Structure Detection on Large Scape Maps with Machine Learning

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Number of core service entries in the NEANIAS Service Portfolio	4 (Section 1.4.1 of DoA): <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Open Science lifecycle support service• EOSC hub RIs and Cloud integration service• AI service• Visualisation service
Number of NEANIAS services accessible in EOSC	9 (at least all the thematic services)

Service Level Management

1. Document control

Process ID	SLM
Process title	Service Level Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The main objectives of SLM are to:

- Maintain the service catalogue (the publicly visible segment of the NEANIAS Service Portfolio).
- Agree service levels with customers by establishing meaningful and sustainable service level agreements (SLAs) with those customers, and supporting operational level agreements (OLAs) and underpinning agreements (UA) with providers. (Note: Many customers will be served using the 'default SLA' of the services. Customer-specific SLAs and OLAs are needed only when the default SLA is not sufficient for a given customer)
- Monitor the delivery of services (performance targets) based on the SLAs and OLAs/UAs, and inform customers and providers in case of non-conformity.

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
SLM1	A service catalogue shall be maintained.	
SLM2	For all services delivered to customers, SLAs shall be in place.	
SLM3	SLAs shall be reviewed at planned intervals.	

D8.2 EOSC service model

SLM4	Service performance shall be evaluated against service targets defined in SLAs.	
SLM5	For supporting services or service components provided by federation members or groups belonging to the same organisation as the service provider or external suppliers, OLAs and UAs shall be agreed.	
SLM6	OLAs and UAs shall be reviewed at planned intervals.	
SLM7	Performance of service components shall be evaluated against operational targets defined in OLAs and UAs.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process
Service catalogue owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain publicly visible information about the NEANIAS service on the NEANIAS Catalogue • Support service owners in the onboarding to EOSC, and monitor the process • Maintain publicly visible information about the NEANIAS services in the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace
SLA/OLA/UA owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signs and maintains an SLA and related OLAs/UAs with a specific customer • Evaluate the fulfilment of the SLA, OLA or UA • Ensure that violations of the targets defined in the SLA, OLA or UA are identified and investigated to prevent future recurrence • Understand new or changed requirements on the SLA, OLA or UA under his/her ownership, and initiate necessary updates or other follow-up actions

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Service portfolio (incl. status of services – e.g. BETA / LIVE / EOSC / RETIRED)
- Service orders
 - From NEANIAS catalogue portal for LIVE services
 - From EOSC Marketplace for EOSC services
- Records of monitoring performance of services (to check compliance with SLAs)
- Service satisfaction reviews from customers (from CRM)

5.2.Activities

1. Add, remove, update a service in the NEANIAS catalogue portal
2. Onboard, remove, update a service in the EOSC Portal
3. Negotiate, sign, update, re-sign an SLA and its underlying OLAs/UAs

5.3.Key outputs

- Service catalogue for NEANIAS catalogue portal (All the live NEANIAS services)
- Service catalogue for EOSC Portal (catalogue and marketplace) (a subset of the live NEANIAS services)
- User guides for service users

D8.2 EOSC service model

- SLA/OLA/UA templates for service providers
- Agreed SLAs, OLAs, UAs

5.4. Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS catalogue portal	The place where profiles of NEANIAS services are gathered (internal database). The public information from the service profiles are published from here to the NEANIAS catalogue portal public front-end. Information for onboarding a NEANIAS service in EOSC can be picked up from here too.
EOSC Portal	Provides interfaces to register new services in EOSC, to update the profiles of existing services.

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: “require from” or “provide to”	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Service Portfolio Management	Service portfolio updates, incl. trigger to register a NEANIAS service in EOSC
Require from	Customer Relationship Management	Outcomes of service satisfaction interviews

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
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D8.2 EOSC service model

Number of services in the NEANIAS catalogue	9 (at least the thematic services): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 underwater: Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data, Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data, Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data • 3 atmospheric: Greenhouse Gases Flux Density Monitoring, Atmospheric Perturbations and Components Monitoring, Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting • 3 space: FAIR Data Management and Visualization, Map Making and Mosaicing of Multidimensional Space Images, Structure Detection on Large Scape Maps with Machine Learning
Number of services in EOSC	9 (all the thematic services)
Number of SLA violations	0

Service Reporting Management

1. Document control

Process ID	SRM
Process title	Service Reporting Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The goal of this process is to specify all service and process reports and ensure they are produced according to specifications in a timely manner to support decision-making.

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
SRM1	Service reports shall be specified and agreed with their recipients.	
SRM2	The specification of each service report shall include its identity, purpose, audience, frequency, content, format and method of delivery.	
SRM3	Service reports shall be produced. Service reporting shall include performance against agreed targets, information about significant events and detected nonconformities.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks

<p>Process Owner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
<p>Process Manager</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process
<p>Service report owner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain the service report specification for the report under his/her ownership • Produce and deliver the service report according to the specification • Ensure that the input / contributions required to produce the report is provided in time Understand new or changed requirements on the report under his/her ownership, and update the report specification accordingly

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Reporting requirements based on process descriptions
- Reporting requirements based on agreed SLAs

5.2. Activities

1. Define, update, terminate a service report
2. Review service report catalogue

5.3. Key outputs

- List of agreed reports with specification and templates

5.4. Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS Teams space	Storage for service reports
Thematic/core service providers' tools	Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: "require from" or "provide to"	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	All processes	Reporting requirements

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Number of overdue or missing reports	0 (in the past 6 months)

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Number of missing process report specification	0
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Customer Relationship Management

1. Document control

Process ID	CRM
Process title	Customer Relationship Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to establish and maintain a good relationship with customers receiving services.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Ensure high levels of customer satisfaction
- Establish proper communication channels with the customer
- Ensure formal customer satisfaction monitoring and complaints filing mechanisms are in place

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
CRM1	Service customers shall be identified.	
CRM2	Communication mechanisms with customers shall be established.	
CRM3	Service reviews with the customers shall be conducted at planned intervals.	
CRM4	Service complaints from customers shall be managed.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process • Ensure that customer complaints are handled according to the process • Coordinate customer satisfaction surveys
(thematic/core service provider) Customer relationship manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for customers of a specific service • Maintain the relationship with customers • Process formal customer complaints • Conduct, moderate and record customer service reviews

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Information on service customers
- Service catalogue
- Customer demands and requirements
- Customer complaints

5.2.Activities

1. Maintain the customer database
2. Manage customer complaints
3. Manage customer satisfaction

5.3.Key outputs

- Service review reports
- Customer complaints records
- Customer satisfaction reports

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presents information about the services that NEANIAS provides to users • Enables service ordering • Provides the interface to users for submitting complaints and requirements about services • Dispatches complaints and requirements about services to the thematic/core service providers for further investigation • Supports customer satisfaction surveys
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS ticketing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of complaints
Thematic/core service providers' tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain customer information • Support customer complaints handling • Enable monitoring and measurement of KPIs • Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: “require from” or “provide to”	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Service level management	Service catalogue, SLAs
Provide to	Change management	Requests for changes required to address a customer complaint/demand/ requirement

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Number of customer satisfaction surveys conducted per year	> 2
Number of complaints raised per service per quarter	< 3

Incident & Service Request Management

1. Document control

Process ID	ISRM
Process title	Incident & Service Request Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to restore normal / agreed service operation within the agreed time after the occurrence of an incident, and to respond to user service requests.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Ensure that incidents are handled in a standardised and efficient manner
- Maintain user and customer satisfaction through efficient and professional handling of service requests

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
ISRM1	All incidents and service requests shall be registered, classified and prioritized in a consistent manner.	
ISRM2	Prioritization of incidents and service requests shall take into account service targets from SLAs.	
ISRM3	Closure of incidents and service requests shall be carried out in a consistent manner.	
ISRM4	Personnel involved in the incident and service request management process shall have access to relevant information including known errors, workarounds, configuration and release information.	

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ISRM5	Users shall be kept informed of the progress of incidents and service requests they have reported.	
ISRM6	There shall be a definition of major incidents and a consistent approach to managing them.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process
(thematic/core service provider)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate and take over overall responsibility for all activities in the lifecycle of a specific incident or service request

<p>Incident owner / service request owner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor the progress of incident resolution or request fulfilment taking into account agreed timeframes • Trigger reminders to those involved in incident resolution or request fulfilment and escalate to the process manager as required • Ensure an adequate level of documentation for the specific incident or service request
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5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Incidents reported by users or identified by the service provider
- Service requests raised by users
- Configuration information

5.2.Activities

1. Manage incidents and service requests
2. Maintain the step-by-step workflows for well-known and recurring incidents and standardized service requests

5.3.Key outputs

- Incident records
- Service request records
- Requests for changes raised to trigger the change management process, in order to commence the fulfilment of service requests
- Up-to-date descriptions of step-by-step workflows for standard incidents and service requests
- Incident reports

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents and service requests • Dispatches incidents records and service requests to the thematic/core service providers for further investigation

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NEANIAS ticketing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors the lifecycle of incidents and service requests
Thematic/core service providers' tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support incident management and request fulfilment • Enable monitoring and measurement of KPIs • Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: "require from" or "provide to"	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Service level management	Incident/ service request response times
Provide to	Change management	Requests for changes required to address an incident/ service request

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Percentage of incidents assigned for investigation within 1 working day from the time they were recorded	> 98%
Percentage of incidents handled within service levels	> 99%
Number of major incidents (i.e. causing unavailability or severe degradation of service) per month	< 3

Change Management

1. Document control

Process ID	CHM
Process title	Change Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to ensure changes to services (or components thereof) are planned, approved, implemented and reviewed in a controlled manner to avoid adverse impact of changes to services or the customers receiving services.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Respond to the customer's changing requirements and demands
- Address changes raised by changing IT requirements of the services
- Minimise risks caused by inadequately managed changes

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
CHM1	All changes shall be registered and classified in a consistent manner.	
CHM2	All changes shall be assessed and approved in a consistent manner.	
CHM3	All changes shall be closed in a consistent manner.	
CHM4	A schedule of changes shall be maintained. It shall contain details of approved changes, and proposed deployment dates, which shall be communicated to interested parties.	

CHM5	For changes of high impact or high risk, the steps required to reverse an unsuccessful change or remedy any negative effects shall be planned and tested.	
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4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process • Ensure that all requests for changes are processed effectively, and in a timely manner • Monitor the overall progress of change evaluation, approval and implementation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review the change records in regular intervals, to identify trends or nonconformities or poor documentation / traceability
(thematic/core service provider) Change owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control and coordinate all activities in the lifecycle of a specific change Monitor the progress of change evaluation and implementation for this change Ensure that the change record is complete and up-to-date at any time from recording

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Requests for changes (RFCs)
- Information on planned releases and deployments

5.2.Activities

- Manage changes
- Maintain the schedule of changes

5.3.Key outputs

- Change records
- Up-to-date schedule of changes

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS ticketing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supports the lifecycle of changes
Thematic/core service providers' tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support change management procedures Enable monitoring and measurement of KPIs Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: “require from” or “provide to”	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Customer Relationship Management	Requests for changes required to address a customer complaint/demand/ requirement
Require from	Release and deployment management	Authorised changes
Require from	Release and deployment management	Updates for the release and deployment activities
Require from	Incident & Service Request Management	Requests for changes required to address an incident/ service request
Require from	Continual Service Improvement Management	Requests for changes required in the context of Continual Service Improvement
Provide to	Release and deployment management	Schedule for release

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Percentage of failed/unsuccessful changes	< 5%
Percentage of changes that remain “open” for more than 6 months	< 3%

Release and deployment management

1. Document control

Process ID	RDM
Process title	Release and deployment management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to bundle changes of one or more CIs to releases, so that these changes can be tested and deployed to the live environment together.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Define release and deployment management plans in consultation with stakeholders, where appropriate
- Ensure that deployment of releases into the live environment is planned and controlled to meet requirements
- Ensure that all release packages can be tracked, installed, tested, verified and/or uninstalled or backed out if appropriate
- Manage change during release and deployment activities

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
RDM1	A release policy shall be defined.	
RDM2	The deployment of new or changed services and service components to the live environment shall be planned with all relevant parties.	
RDM3	Releases shall be built and tested prior to being deployed.	

RDM4	Acceptance criteria for each release shall be agreed with all relevant parties. Before deployment the release shall be verified against the agreed acceptance criteria and approved.	
RDM5	Deployment preparation shall consider steps to be taken in case of unsuccessful deployment to reduce the impact on services and customers.	
RDM6	Releases shall be evaluated for success or failure.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process
(thematic/core service provider) Release owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control and coordinate the activities in the lifecycle of a specific release, including planning, building, testing and deploying Ensure that the required documentation of the release (including release plans) is complete and of adequate quality Act as a single point of contact for the release for all stakeholders of this release

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Authorized change
- Service design package including the requirements for the service and the service acceptance criteria
- Release policy
- Exit and entry criteria for each stage of the process

5.2.Activities

- Plan the release and its deployment, based on authorised changes
- Build the release
- Test the release
- Deploy the release into the live environment – Update the service catalogue
- Review release deployment

5.3.Key outputs

- New, changed or retired services
- Fully tested service capability and environment
- Release package (baselined)
- Service transition report
- New or updated SLAs and OLAs, if applicable

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
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NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS catalogue portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the interface to users for submitting incidents related to a service release • Dispatches incidents records to the thematic/core service providers for further investigation
Thematic/core service providers' tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain information about the services and their releases • Enable monitoring and measurement of KPIs • Support incident management • Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: "require from" or "provide to"	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	Change management	Authorised changes
Provide to	Change management	Updates for the release and deployment activities
Provide to	Service level management	Information about the new or changed service to update the service catalogue

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Percentage of releases that successfully updated the service catalogue before made available to the users	100%

D8.2 EOSC service model

Percentage of releases deployed into the live environment without any performance and functionality issues	> 95%
Number of incidents related to the performance and functionality of each new release	< 5

Continual Service Improvement Management

1. Document control

Process ID	CSI
Process title	Continual Service Improvement Management
Process owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Process status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Goal & objectives

The primary goal of this process is to identify, prioritize, plan, implement and review improvements to services and service management.

The main objectives of the process are to:

- Address nonconformities and deficiencies related to the IT Service Management Framework
- Address deficiencies in the performance of services
- Exploit opportunities for improvement

3. Requirements

Ref.	Description	Status
CSI1	Opportunities for improvement shall be identified and registered.	
CSI2	Opportunities for improvement shall be evaluated and approved in a consistent manner.	

4. Role model

The following roles are relevant in the context of this process.

Role	Responsibilities/ Tasks
Process Owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for concerns in the context of governing the process • Define and approve goals and policies in the context of the process according to the overall SMS goals and policies • Nominate the process manager, and ensure he / she is competent to fulfil this role • Approve changes / improvements to the operational process, such as (significant) changes to the process definition • Decide on the provision of resources dedicated to the process and its activities • Based on process monitoring and reviews, decide on necessary changes in the process-specific goals, policies and provided resources
Process Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as the primary contact point for operational concerns in the context of the process • Maintain the process definition / description and ensure it is available to relevant persons • Maintain an adequate level of awareness and competence of the people involved in the process • Monitor and keep track of the process execution and results (incl. process reviews) • Report on process performance to the process owner • Escalate to the process owner, if necessary • Identify opportunities for improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the process • Review the status and progress of ongoing improvements in regular intervals
(thematic/core service provider or process manager) Improvement owner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain the improvement under his/her ownership • Coordinate the activities to implement the improvement

5. Process overview

5.1.Key inputs

- Identified nonconformities as well as deficiencies in effectiveness and efficiency of ITSM processes, and resulting opportunities for improvement

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- Identified deficiencies in the performance of services or supporting service components, and resulting opportunities for improvement

5.2.Activities

1. Manage improvements
2. Review the status and progress of improvements

5.3.Key outputs

- Requests for changes raised to trigger the change management process, in order to implement improvements
- Reports on the status and progress of improvements

5.4.Supporting tools

Tool	Functionality
NEANIAS wiki	Stores information about the processes of the NEANIAS service management system
NEANIAS ticketing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports the lifecycle of CSI opportunities
Thematic/core service providers' tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support CSI management procedures • Enable monitoring and measurement of KPIs • Provide service reports

6. Interfaces

The following table summarizes the most important interfaces (i.e. information or control flows) between this process and other processes and their related activities.

Interface type: "require from" or "provide to"	Interfacing process	Description of the interface
Require from	All processes	Opportunities for improvement of the services and the service management framework
Provide to	Change Management	Requests for changes required in the context of Continual Service Improvement

7. Key performance indicators

The following key performance indicators are used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the process.

KPI	Target
Percentage of CSI opportunities that remain “open” for more than 6 months	< 5%

A2: NEANIAS service management procedures

Handling customer complaints

1. Document control

Procedure ID	CRM1
Procedure title	Handling customer complaints
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS handles user complaints related to its services.

This procedure supports the Customer Relationship Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is triggered by customer (user) complaints.

4. Steps to be performed

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Record a complaint on NEANIAS catalogue portal	Service user (customer)	
2	Open ticket at NEANIAS ticketing system – Set status to “open”	Automatically	Through integration of NEANIAS catalogue portal with the ticketing system
3	Notify partner responsible for the specific service – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	

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	system to “assigned to service owner”		
4	Investigate a complaint – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under investigation”	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	Configuration information, Known errors etc. shall be consulted during investigation
5	Raise a Request for Change – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “change requested”	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	If applicable
6	Resolve a complaint – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “resolved”	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	
7	Close a complaint – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “closed”	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	
8	Update customer complaints records	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	
9	Notify the customer who raised the complaint	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	

Reviewing customer satisfaction

1. Document control

Procedure ID	CRM2
Procedure title	Reviewing customer satisfaction
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS performs customer satisfaction surveys related to its services.

This procedure supports the Customer Relationship Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by one of the following events:

- Customer relationship managers of the NEANIAS Resource (service) providers (at planned intervals or ad-hoc)
- Customer complaints (ad-hoc reviews)

4. Steps to be performed

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Plan a customer satisfaction survey	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	For which service or set of services, duration (from-to), topics/ questions
2	Create the customer satisfaction survey	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	

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3	Notify customers to participate to the survey	Automatically	Based on the services included in the survey
4	Analyse customer satisfaction survey results	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	
5	Raise a Request for Change (or Opportunity for Improvement)	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	If applicable
6	Update customer satisfaction reports	Customer relationship manager of the Resource (service) provider	

Handling Incidents & Service Requests

1. Document control

Procedure ID	ISRM1
Procedure title	Handling Incidents & Service Requests
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS handles incidents and requests related to its services.

This procedure supports the Incident & Service Request Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by one of the following events:

- Incidents reported by users or identified by the service provider
- Service requests raised by users

4. Steps to be performed

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Record an incident or service request on NEANIAS catalogue portal	Service user (customer), Resource (service) provider	
2	Open ticket at NEANIAS ticketing system – Set status to “open”	Automatically	Through integration of NEANIAS catalogue portal with the ticketing system

D8.2 EOSC service model

3	Notify partner responsible for the specific service – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “assigned to service owner”	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	
4	Classify an incident or service request	Automatically	Incidents and requests will be classified according the service(s) they refer to, during their initial recording
5	Prioritize an incident or service request at NEANIAS ticketing system	Resource provider (service)	Based on the impact and urgency of the incident/ service request (refer to Ch.5)
6	Investigate an incident or service request – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under investigation”	Resource provider (service)	Configuration information, Known errors etc. shall be consulted during investigation
7	Raise a Request for Change – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “change requested”	Resource provider (service)	If applicable
8	Resolve an incident or service request – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “resolved”	Resource provider (service)	
9	Close an incident or service request – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “closed”	Resource provider (service)	
10	Update incident/ service requests records	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	

11	Notify the person who reported the incident or service request	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	
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5. Prioritisation matrix

For the prioritisation of incidents or service requests, NEANIAS thematic/ core service providers shall develop an urgency / impact matrix like the one in Figure 9, which shall be populated with resolution times according to the service levels applicable to each service. To be noted that the resolution times in the following table are indicative and only for illustration purposes. Priority 1 incidents shall be considered as major incidents.

	Impact		
Urgency	High	Medium	Low
High	P1: Resolution in 1 day	P2: Resolution in 3 days	P3: Resolution in 5 days
Medium	P2: Resolution in 3 days	P3: Resolution in 5 days	P4: Resolution in 8 days
Low	P3: Resolution in 5 days	P4: Resolution in 8 days	P5: Resolution in 15 days

Figure 9: Prioritisation matrix

Handling Changes

1. Document control

Procedure ID	CHM1
Procedure title	Handling Changes
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS handles changes related to its services and their service components.

This procedure supports the Change Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by one of the following events:

- Requests for changes (RFCs) raised by other service management processes, e.g. incident & service request management, Customer Relationship Management.
- Authorised changes by the Release and deployment management process.

4. Steps to be performed

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Record an RFC at NEANIAS ticketing system – Set status to “open”	Resource (service) provider	
2	Classify an RFC at NEANIAS ticketing system	Automatically	RFCs will be classified according the service(s) they refer to, during their initial recording

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3	Evaluate an RFC – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under evaluation”	Resource provider	(service)	Urgency, criticality, impact, risk and other factors shall be considered. Supporting services, components or CIs, and dependencies in general, shall be taken into account.
4	Approve/ reject an RFC – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “approved”/ “rejected”	Resource provider	(service)	
5	Implement & Test the Change at the development environment – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under development”	Resource provider	(service)	For approved changes
6	Sign-off the Change – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “planned for deployment”	Resource provider	(service)	
7	Notify the Release owner of the specific service	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system		The change will be included in the next release of the service
8	Update change records	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system		For both approved and rejected RFCs

Building and Deploying Releases

1. Document control

Procedure ID	RDM1
Procedure title	Building and Deploying Releases
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS plans, builds, tests and deploys new service releases to the live environment.

This procedure supports the Release and Deployment Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by authorised changes, evaluated, approved and implemented by the Change Management process.

4. Steps to be performed

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Plan the release and its deployment – Define acceptance criteria for the release – Prepare roll-back plans for unsuccessful deployment	Release owner of a specific service	Upon notification by NEANIAS ticketing system that a Change (or a number of changes) has been implemented
2	Build the release at the development environment	Release owner of a specific service	

D8.2 EOSC service model

3	Test the release at the development environment	Release owner of a specific service	During release testing, dependencies of a service on other (core) services (e.g. AAI, data sharing) shall be taken into account, therefore integration testing shall also be executed.
4	Update service documentation, e.g. SLAs, privacy policies, Terms of Use, tutorials, change log, FAQs, etc., based on the changes introduced by the new release	Release owner of a specific service	Without publishing the information on the NEANIAS catalogue at this stage
5	Update service model on the NEANIAS catalogue	Release owner of a specific service	Without publishing the updated info on the NEANIAS catalogue at this stage
6	Schedule the deployment of the release into the live environment -	Release owner of a specific service	
7	Inform service users about the deployment schedule	Automatically	
8	Deploy the release into the live environment according to the schedule – Update the service model on NEANIAS service catalogue – Publish updated service documentation	Release owner of a specific service	
9	Review release deployment – Sign-off the successful deployment of the release	Release owner of a specific service	Using the defined acceptance criteria
10	Inform service users about the availability of a new release	Automatically	

Handling Improvements

1. Document control

Procedure ID	CSI1
Procedure title	Handling Improvements
Procedure owner	NEANIAS
Version	1.0
Procedure status	DRAFT
Last date of change	21/12/2020
Version & change tracking	1.0 Initial draft

2. Overview & context

The purpose of this procedure is to describe how NEANIAS handles improvements related to its services and their service components, as well to the service management system itself.

This procedure supports the Continual Service Improvement Management process.

3. Triggers

The execution of this procedure is usually triggered by one of the following events:

- Nonconformities/ deficiencies in effectiveness and efficiency of ITSM processes.
- Deficiencies in the performance of services or supporting service components.
- Opportunities for improvement resulting from the above.

4. Steps to be performed

In the context of NEANIAS service management framework, opportunities for improvement (OFIs) shall be treated as a special type of Requests for Change. Therefore the steps of the procedure for Handling Changes apply as follows:

Step ID	Description	Responsible	Comments
1	Record an RFC (of type OFI) at NEANIAS ticketing system – Set status to “open”	Resource provider (service)	

D8.2 EOSC service model

2	Classify an RFC (of type OFI) at NEANIAS ticketing system	Automatically	<p>OFIs will be classified according the service(s) they refer to, during their initial recording.</p> <p>For OFIs related to the service management processes, appropriate classification will be used.</p>
3	Evaluate an RFC (of type OFI) – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under evaluation”	Resource provider (service)	<p>Urgency, criticality, impact, risk and other factors shall be considered.</p> <p>Supporting services, components or CIs, and dependencies in general, shall be taken into account.</p>
4	Approve/ reject an RFC (of type OFI) – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “approved”/ “rejected”	Resource provider (service)	
5	Implement & Test the Change at the development environment – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under development”	Resource provider (service)	<p>The approved OFIs become approved Changes.</p> <p>For approved changes related to services.</p>
6	Sign-off the Change – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “planned for deployment”	Resource provider (service)	
7	Notify the Release owner of the specific service	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	The change will be included in the next release of the service

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8	Update change records	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	For both approved and rejected RFCs (of type OFI)
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In case an approved change is related to the service management framework of NEANIAS, the procedure follows the alternative path (from step 5 onwards):

5	Implement the Change at the NEANIAS service management framework – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “under development”	Manager of a specific service management process	The approved OFIs become approved Changes. For approved changes related to the NEANIAS service management framework.
6	Sign-off the Change – Change status at NEANIAS ticketing system to “planned for deployment”	Owner of a specific service management process	
7	Update NEANIAS service management framework documentation	Manager of a specific service management process	On NEANIAS wiki system
8	Notify Resource (service) providers	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	
9	Update change records	Automatically by NEANIAS ticketing system	For both approved and rejected RFCs (of type OFI)

Annex B: NEANIAS service models

Annex B1: Provider Profiles

1. ATHENA

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Athena Research and Innovation Center in Information and Communication Technologies
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	ATHENA
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.athenarc.gr/en
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Public Legal Entity under Private Law
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	<p>The mission of Athena RC is to conduct outstanding research in Informatics and Computational Sciences and to ensure this research has an impact on society, tackling global challenges and addressing local needs. Athena RC studies a broad spectrum of research issues within these fields, including some raised by other sciences, industrial applications, or societal challenges.</p> <p>The scope of activities of Athena RC includes all Information and Communication Technologies, from the perspective of both Computer Science and Computational Sciences, and covering all software and hardware aspects. These include all areas of informatics, data science, robotics, automation, signal processing, artificial intelligence, networking and digital communication, and modelling.</p> <p>Multidisciplinarity is at the foundation of the research philosophy of Athena RC, which carries out R&D both at the level of information technology itself and at the level of specific applications. Computational sciences thus form a strong component of the Athena RC activities, including - but not being limited to - computational linguistics, archaeology, engineering, medicine, biology, biodiversity,</p>

D8.2 EOSC service model

		<p>earth observation, space science, mechanics, and the arts.</p> <p>Together with research, innovation is also a fundamental pillar of the mission of Athena RC. Research institutes, spin-off companies, and three highly-specialised clusters in knowledge-intensive thematic sectors create a fertile technological innovation ecosystem within the Center. Collaboration between all actors, including systematic efforts to bring research results to market, has always been mutually beneficial.</p>
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://www.athenarc.gr/sites/all/themes/aohna/images/athena-logo-symbol.svg
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	https://youtu.be/1oJlMlavgknc
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Engineering & Technology
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Electrical, Electronic & Information Engineering
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Data-Technologies, Language-Technologies, Cultural-Heritage, Environmental-Technologies, Technologies-for-the-Industry
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Artemidos 6 & Epidavrou
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	15125
EPP.LOI.3	City	Marousi
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Attica
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Greece
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Yannis
EPP.COI.3	Email	loannidis
EPP.COI.4	Phone	
EPP.COI.5	Position	Director General, President
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	

D8.2 EOSC service model

EPP.COI.7	Last Name	
EPP.COI.8	Email	info@athena-innovation.gr
EPP.COI.9	Phone	
EPP.COI.10	Position	
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	ISO 9001:2008
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	Distributed
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	Data, Computing & Digital Research Infrastructures
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	Node
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	Basic research, Applied research, Technological development
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

2. CITE

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Communication & Information Technologies Experts SA Consulting and Development Services
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	CITE
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.cite.gr
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Private Company
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	CITE is an SME activating in the domain of ICT systems engineering, research and consulting.

D8.2 EOSC service model

		<p>Commercial activities of the company include large-scale systems design and implementation, techno-economic analysis of ICT systems and services and systems' testing and quality assurance. Research and innovation activities address cloud and distributed processing, data management, information retrieval, modeling/simulation etc. CITE aims to bring beyond-state-of-the-art concepts into production processes and enhance research processes with production level quality. CITE is powered by highly skilled workforce, ca 40 employees and consultants, the majority being postgraduate degree holders with substantial experience in research and innovation projects, both at European and National level. CITE is advocate of dependable, reproducible research and contributes to the vision with FOSS Software and services that empower researchers and institutes to onboard the worldwide movement of Open Science.</p>
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://www.cite.gr/sites/default/files/logo_%28480%29.png
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Engineering & Technology
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Electrical, Electronic & Information Technology
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Data-Management Data-Management-Planning Distributed-Processing Authentication-Authorization Systems Security
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	ETHNIKIS ANTISTASEOS 178
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	16122
EPP.LOI.3	City	KAISARIANI
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Attica
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Greece
Contact Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

Main Contact/Provider Manager

EPP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios Kakalettris
EPP.COI.3	Email	gkakas@cite.gr
EPP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
EPP.COI.5	Position	Chief Research Information Officer (CRIO)
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Georgios
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Kakalettris
EPP.COI.8	Email	gkakas@cite.gr
EPP.COI.9	Phone	+302121020553
EPP.COI.10	Position	Chief Research Information Officer (CRIO)
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	ISO 9001:2015
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

3. CORONIS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	
EPP.BAI.1	Name	CORONIS
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	CORONIS
EPP.BAI.3	Website	http://coronis.es

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EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Private Company
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	Coronis Computing SL is a spin-off company of the Computer Vision and Robotics group (VICOROB) of the University of Girona, in Spain. It is mainly focused on research, development and technology transfer activities, specialized in computer vision and machine learning technologies.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	http://logos.coronis.es
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	http://coronis.es
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology, Medical & Health Sciences, Agricultural Sciences, Humanities
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Mathematics, Computer and information sciences, Earth and related environmental sciences, Biological sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering, Medical engineering, Environmental engineering, Environmental biotechnology, Medical biotechnology, Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, Agricultural biotechnology, History and archaeology
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Computer Vision, Machine Learning, Cloud Services
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Parc Científic i Tecnològic UdG - Edifici Giroemprèn, C/ Pic de Peguera, 15
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	17003
EPP.LOI.3	City	Girona
EPP.LOI.4	Region	
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Spain
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Josep
EPP.COI.3	Email	josep.quintana@coronis.es
EPP.COI.4	Phone	+34 972 18 3241

D8.2 EOSC service model

EPP.COI.5	Position	Head of R&D Department
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Josep
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Quintana
EPP.COI.8	Email	josep.quintana@coronis.es
EPP.COI.9	Phone	+34 972 18 3241
EPP.COI.10	Position	Head of R&D Department
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

4. GARR

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	GARR
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Consortium GARR
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	GARR
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.garr.it
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Other
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	Consortium GARR (GARR) is a non-profit association founded under the auspices of the Ministry of Education, University and Research.

D8.2 EOSC service model

		The founding members are CNR, ENEA, INFN and CRUI Foundation, representing all Italian universities. GARR is the ultra-broadband network dedicated to the Italian research and education community. Its main objective is to provide high-performance connectivity and to develop innovative services for the daily activities of researchers, professors and students as well as for international collaboration. Moreover, GARR provisions to its users a virtualisation infrastructure based on five data centres located in five different sites contributing to a resource pool of 9000 virtual cores, 66 TB of RAM and more than 10 PB of storage space.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://www.garr.it/images/logo_medio_garr.png
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	https://cloud.garr.it/doc/videos/
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Generic
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Generic
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	network, cloud, NREN
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Via dei Tizii, 6
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	00185
EPP.LOI.3	City	Rome
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Latium
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Italy
Contact Information		

Main Contact/Provider Manager

EPP.COI.1	First Name	Federico
		Ruggieri
EPP.COI.3	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
EPP.COI.4	Phone	+39 06 4962 2000
EPP.COI.5	Position	Director and Coordinator
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Claudio
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Pisa
EPP.COI.8	Email	cloud-support@garr.it

D8.2 EOSC service model

EPP.COI.9	Phone	
EPP.COI.10	Position	Distributed Computing and Storage department
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	GÉANT
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	GÉANT
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	Distributed
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	Information Science & Technology
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	Communication Networks, Distributed Computing Facilities
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

5. Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica (INAF)

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	INAF
EPP.BAI.3	Website	http://www.inaf.it/en
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Public Legal Entity
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	Italian research institute in astronomy and astrophysics, founded in 1999. INAF funds and operates twenty separate research facilities, which in turn employ scientists, engineers and technical staff. The research they perform covers most areas of astronomy, ranging from: Galaxies and Cosmology; the Sun and the Solar System; Stars, Stellar Populations and the Interstellar

D8.2 EOSC service model

		Medium; Relativistic and Particle Astrophysics; Advanced Technologies and Instrumentation.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	http://www.inaf.it/it/sedi/sede-centrale-nuova/presidenza/ufficio-relazioni-con-il-pubblico-e-la-stampa/uso-del-logo_old/uso%20del%20logo/immagini/inaf-circ-colore.gif
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	https://youtu.be/F4DJ8IXePWU https://www.media.inaf.it/
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Physical Sciences, Computer & Information Sciences
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Astronomy, Astrophysics, Radio Astronomy, Virtual Observatory, Galactic Plane
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Viale del Parco Mellini n°84
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	136
EPP.LOI.3	City	ROMA
EPP.LOI.4	Region	
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Marco Tavani
EPP.COI.3	Email	inaf.europe@inaf.it
EPP.COI.4	Phone	
EPP.COI.5	Position	President / Legal Signatory
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Chiara
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Guccione
EPP.COI.8	Email	USC-Bandi@inaf.it
EPP.COI.9	Phone	+39 06 35533 341
EPP.COI.10	Position	H2020 Office

D8.2 EOSC service model

Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	Italy
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	Physical Sciences & Engineering
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	Physics, Astronomy, Astrophysics and Mathematics
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	Basic research, Applied Research, technological research
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

6. Jacobs University Bremen

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	JUNI
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Jacobs University Bremen
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	JacobsUni
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://jacobs-university.de
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	gGmbH (non-profit company with limited liability under German law)
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	

D8.2 EOSC service model

EPP.CLI.3	Tags	
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Campus Ring 1
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	28759
EPP.LOI.3	City	Bremen
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Bremen
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Germany
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	
EPP.COI.3	Email	
EPP.COI.4	Phone	
EPP.COI.5	Position	
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Angelo
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Rossi
EPP.COI.8	Email	an.rossi@jacobs-university.de
EPP.COI.9	Phone	
EPP.COI.10	Position	
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	Jacobs University Bremen (providing science pipelines) & MEE0 (providing cloud infrastructure)
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	Germany
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	Europlanet Society
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	Data, Computing
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	Sciences and Humanities
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	

D8.2 EOSC service model

EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	Basic and applied research
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

7. Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation (MEEO)

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	MEEO
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	MEEO
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.meeo.it/
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Private Company
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	MEEO, born in 2004 with the aim to develop and commercialize products and services within the Earth Observation, is a privately-held company devoted to the development and implementation of products and services based on remote sensing of the Earth-Atmosphere system. MEEO is able to provide a wide range of services and products “ready” (off the shelf) based on analysis of multispectral, multisensor and multitemporal satellite data for environmental monitoring, land management and agriculture.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	www.meeo.it , https://www.facebook.com/meeosrl , https://twitter.com/meeosrl , https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqy-bd6CpXMOIRqfHmBqIZw/featured
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Engineering & Technology, Natural Sciences
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Earth and related environmental sciences, Other engineering and technology sciences
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Earth Observation, Remote Sensing, Cloud computing, Information Science, Big Data, Datacube, Cloud services

D8.2 EOSC service model

Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Via Ercole I d'Este, 6/A
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	44121
EPP.LOI.3	City	Ferrara
EPP.LOI.4	Region	
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Simone Mantovani
EPP.COI.3	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
EPP.COI.4	Phone	05321861501
EPP.COI.5	Position	Managing Director
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Simone
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Mantovani
EPP.COI.8	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
EPP.COI.9	Phone	05321861501
EPP.COI.10	Position	Managing Director
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	OGC Associate Member, Climate-KIC Affiliated Partner
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	Distributed
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	Technological development

EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

8. National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	
EPP.BAI.1	Name	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	NKUA
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://en.uoa.gr/
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	The National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA) is a learner-focused and research-oriented public university covering a wide spectrum of scientific fields. Its vision is to promote excellence in education and innovation in research, scholarly and other creative endeavours and also be actively involved with local, national and global communities.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://en.uoa.gr/fileadmin/user_upload/uoa_logo_eng.svg
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Christou Lada Str.
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	10561
EPP.LOI.3	City	Athens
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Attica
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Greece
Contact Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Nikolaos
EPP.COI.3	Email	vrec-rd@uoa.gr
EPP.COI.4	Phone	
EPP.COI.5	Position	
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Nikolaos
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Voulgaris
EPP.COI.8	Email	vrec-rd@uoa.gr
EPP.COI.9	Phone	
EPP.COI.10	Position	
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

9. SZTAKI

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	SZTAKI
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Institute for Computer Science and Control
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	SZTAKI
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.sztaki.hu/en

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EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Public Company
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	The SZTAKI is a research institute, governed by the Eötvös Loránd Research Network. Upon the charge by the Secretary-general of the Academy, the supervision of the scientific activity pursued at the Institute is provided by the Board of the Institute. SZTAKI is the acronym of the Hungarian name of the institute, while its full English name is "Institute for Computer Science and Control".
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://www.sztaki.hu/sites/default/files/2019/page/media/logo_2019_1.zip
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	https://www.youtube.com/user/mtasztakipr
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Kende u. 13-17.
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	1111
EPP.LOI.3	City	Budapest
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Pest
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Hungary
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Róbert
EPP.COI.2	Last Name	Lovas
EPP.COI.3	Email	robert.lovas@sztaki.hu
EPP.COI.4	Phone	+36 1 279 6275
EPP.COI.5	Position	deputy director
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	József
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Kovács
EPP.COI.8	Email	jozsef.kovacs@sztaki.hu
EPP.COI.9	Phone	+36 1 279 6066

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EPP.COI.10	Position	senior research fellow
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	ISO 9001:2015
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	SZTAKI
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	Hungary
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	EGI, GEANT, RDA
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	Distributed
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	Information Science & Technology
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	Basic research, Applied research, Technological development
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	Yes

10. UBIWHERE

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	Ubiwhere
EPP.BAI.1	Name	Ubiwhere, Lda.
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	UW
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.ubiwhere.com/
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME)
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	Founded in 2007, Ubiwhere is focused on Research, Development and Innovation of software-based solutions in the areas of Smart Cities, Telecom and Future Internet, and New Technologies. As an innovative and technological company, the skills of our team are one of our differentiating factors. We have

D8.2 EOSC service model

		the innate desire of changing the World, the reason why we create, design and develop solutions which aim at improving everyone's lives.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B6IWGlcmEolHUWdmOS1TaHJxUDQ/view?usp=sharing
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1rnMyXFariVUWmJ1GOZo_G6kWCgvhrj5/view?usp=sharing
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Information Science and Technology
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Smart Cities, Telecom and Future Internet
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	Open data, open science, web development, artificial intelligence, REST APIs, forecasting, atmospheric
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Travessa Senhor das Barrocas, 38
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	3800-075
EPP.LOI.3	City	Aveiro
EPP.LOI.4	Region	Aveiro
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Portugal
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Ricardo
EPP.COI.2	Last Name	Vitorino
EPP.COI.3	Email	rvitorino@ubiwhere.com
EPP.COI.4	Phone	00351239151993
EPP.COI.5	Position	Head of Innovation
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	Ricardo
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	Vitorino
EPP.COI.8	Email	rvitorino@ubiwhere.com
EPP.COI.9	Phone	00351239151993
EPP.COI.10	Position	Head of Innovation
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	Operational
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	

Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	Ubiwhere
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	Portugal
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	PROEF Group
EPP.OTH.4	Networks	AIOTI, BDVA, EIP-SCC, ERTICO, ETSI, 5G-PPP
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	Distributed
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

11. University of Milano-Bicocca (UNIMIB)

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
EPP.BAI.0	ID	UNIMIB
EPP.BAI.1	Name	University of Milano-Bicocca
EPP.BAI.2	Abbreviation	UNIMIB
EPP.BAI.3	Website	https://www.unimib.it/
EPP.BAI.4	Legal Entity	Y
EPP.BAI.5	Legal Status	Public Legal Entity
Marketing Information		
EPP.MRI.1	Description	The University of Milano – Bicocca is a young and competitive university in Italy which, in few years, has established itself in the Italian and international landscapes. It was ranked 2nd best Italian university among those comparable in size, according to ANVUR (national agency for the rating of university quality and research) and 55th on the list for best 150 universities less than 50 years' old, according to THE Times Higher Education. The university is composed of fourteen departments (11 out of 14 are awarded "of excellence") and by more than 30 research centers. The university has three main target

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		objectives in its mission: teaching, research and technology transfer.
EPP.MRI.2	Logo	https://en.unimib.it/sites/sten/files/logo_0.png
EPP.MRI.3	Multimedia	
Classification Information		
EPP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Information Science & Technology, Earth and Environmental Sciences
EPP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.CLI.3	Tags	
Location Information		
EPP.LOI.1	Street Name and Number	Piazza dell'Ateneo Nuovo, 1
EPP.LOI.2	Postal Code	20126
EPP.LOI.3	City	Milan
EPP.LOI.4	Region	
EPP.LOI.5	Country	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Provider Manager		
EPP.COI.1	First Name	Giuseppe Vizzari
EPP.COI.3	Email	giuseppe.vizzari@unimib.it
EPP.COI.4	Phone	
EPP.COI.5	Position	Coordinator of UNIMIB research unit in NEANIAS project
Public Contact		
EPP.COI.6	First Name	
EPP.COI.7	Last Name	
EPP.COI.8	Email	giuseppe.vizzari@unimib.it
EPP.COI.9	Phone	
EPP.COI.10	Position	
Maturity Information		
EPP.MTI.1	Life Cycle Status	
EPP.MTI.2	Certifications	
Other Information		
EPP.OTH.1	Hosting Legal Entity	
EPP.OTH.2	Participating Countries	
EPP.OTH.3	Affiliations	

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EPP.OTH.4	Networks	
EPP.OTH.5	Structure Type	
EPP.OTH.6	ESFRI Domain	
EPP.OTH.7	ESFRI Type	
EPP.OTH.8	MERIL Scientific Domain	
EPP.OTH.9	MERIL Scientific Subdomain	
EPP.OTH.10	Areas of Activity	
EPP.OTH.11	Societal Grand Challenges	
EPP.OTH.12	National Roadmaps	

Annex B2: Resource (Service) Profiles

1. Underwater sector

UW-MOS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	UW-Mos
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	CORONIS
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CORONIS
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The Seafloor Mosaicing from Optical Data service aims to provide an operational solution for large area representation (in the order of tens of thousands of images) of the, predominantly flat, seafloor addressing also visibility limitations from the underwater medium.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Underwater Mapping Service
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://citegr.sharepoint.com/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fteams%2Fh2020%2Dneanias%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP06%2DCoreServices%2FCore%20Services%2FC1%2DCommonUIComponents%2FLogos%5FRaw%2FUNDERWATER%2FU2%2FNeanias%5FUnderwater%5FMOS%2Esvg&parent=%2Fteams%2Fh2020%2Dneanias%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP06%2DCoreServices%2FCore%20Services%2FC1%2DCommonUIComponents%2FLogos%5FRaw%2FUNDERWATER%2FU2
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:p:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BB4DDDA2E-51DF-4BB5-B8FB-A0E28FF6FFE0%7D&file=NEANIAS-General Meeting 20201119 WP2 U2 Coronis.pptx&action=edit&mobileredirect=true
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology, Humanities
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Earth and related environmental sciences, Biological sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering, Environmental engineering, Environmental biotechnology, History and archaeology
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	2D /3D Digitalization

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ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Individual Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Reserach projects, Innovators, Scientists, Businesses, SMEs
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Underwater Mapping Service
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Spain (ES)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Ricard
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Campos
ERP.COI.3	Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+34 972 18 32 41
ERP.COI.5	Position	Research & Development Engineer
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CORONIS
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Ricard
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Campos
ERP.COI.9	Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+34 972 18 32 41
ERP.COI.11	Position	Research & Development Engineer
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CORONIS
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Bootstrap, Flask, Celery, Jinja2, Redis, uWSGI, nginx, opencv, openmvg, openmvs
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	15/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	

D8.2 EOSC service model

Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free (requires authentication)
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

UW-MAP

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	UW-MAP
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	NKUA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://uw-map.neanias.eu
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes, validated for archeological, geo-hazards, energy, and other applications.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Seabed Classification from Multispectral Multibeam Data

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://uw-map.neanias.eu/static/images/Neanias_Underwater_MM_mod.svg
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences, Environmental engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Application, Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Utilities, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Image/data analysis
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Individual Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Reserach projects, Innovators, Scientists, Businesses, SMEs
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Seabed Classification, Multispectral Multibeam Data, Mapping
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Konstantinos
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Karantzalos
ERP.COI.3	Email	karank@central.ntua.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	:+302107721673
ERP.COI.5	Position	Researcher
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	NTUA, ATHENA
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Konstantinos
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Karantzalos
ERP.COI.9	Email	karank@central.ntua.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	:+302107721673
ERP.COI.11	Position	Researcher
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	NTUA, ATHENA
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	

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ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Bootstrap, Flask, Celery, Jinja2, Redis, uWSGI, nginx
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.2
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	15/12/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	Upgrade UI, add resources, correction of minor bugs
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

2. Atmospheric sector

Atmo-FLUD

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ATMO-FLUD
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	ATHENA, NKUA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://atmo-flud.neanias.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	ATMO-FLUD provides a set of algorithms for the calculation of flux densities of Sensible Heat, Latent Heat, Turbulent Kinetic Energy and other scalars like GHGs. The input data to the service is user provided although test data are available for trial runs. Real data should be experimentally obtained by the user bearing in mind that the fundamental method employed in this service is the "Eddy Covariance".
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Calculation of Flux Densities
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://atmo-flud.neanias.eu/static/images/Atmo-FLUD.svg
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences, Environmental engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis, Aggregators & Integrators
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Visualization, Data extrapolation, Services
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Reserach projects, Innovators, Businesses
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Flux densities
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Spyros
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Rapsomanikis
ERP.COI.3	Email	rapso@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	

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ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Spyros
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Rapsomanikis
ERP.COI.9	Email	rapso@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	atmo_flud_helpdesk@lists.athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	atmo_flud_helpdesk@lists.athenarc.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Bootstrap, Flask, Jinja2, Redis, Unicorn, nginx, PostgreSQL, Kubernetes
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Atmo-Stress

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ATMO-STRESS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	UNIMIB
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	NKUA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	ATMO-STRESS shows regional trends on 2-D gridded map (x-y plane) and can reconstruct a paleostress trajectory map by implementing the following two different methods (Lee and Angelier, 1993): (i) polynomial and (ii) distance weighted interpolation. It represents an upgrade of the already existing "Lissage" program (Lee and Angelier, 1994), which presented several limitations: it has been written using the Turbo C language, it is not user-friendly, it does not consider different data sources, and it cannot manage a large amount of data. All these issues are overcome thanks to ATMO-STRESS service, which also allows to download output maps in formats compatible with GIS environments (e.g. shp, kml)
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	ATMO-STRESS service for reconstruction of stress trajectories map
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://atmo-stress.neanias.eu/static/images/Neanias_Atmosphere_Atmo-STRESS_mod.svg
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Application, Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Utilities, Image/data analysis, 2D/3D Digitisation
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research community, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Stress-field, 2D-Reconstruction

D8.2 EOSC service model

Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Alessandro
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Tibaldi
ERP.COI.3	Email	alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 3928633333
ERP.COI.5	Position	Ordinary Professor
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	University of Milan-Bicocca
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Alessandro
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Tibaldi
ERP.COI.9	Email	alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+39 3928633333
ERP.COI.11	Position	Ordinary Professor
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	University of Milan-Bicocca
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	JupyterLab
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	18/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	First production release
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	None
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	None
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-1-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Atmo-Seism

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ATMO-SEISM
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	UNIMIB
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	NKUA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	http://atmo-seism.neanias.eu
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	ATMO-SEISM is a service for scientists to design, develop and test the correlation between gas measurements, atmospheric conditions and earthquake data. The considered earthquake parameters are: the earthquake Magnitude, the distance between the hypocentre and the gas emission site, and data and time of the seismic event. This service is focused especially on radon, but it could be possibly used also for other gases emitted in volcanic areas, like SO ₂ and CO ₂ . The language that is used is Python, one of the most popular languages in data science. Jupyter Hub is a multi-user development environment using the IPython interface, allowing

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		code implementation and interpretation using a web interface.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	ATMO-SEISM service for correlation between gas emission, atmospheric conditions and earthquakes
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://citegr.sharepoint.com/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fteams%2Fh2020%2Dneanias%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP06%2DCoreServices%2FCore%20Services%2FC1%2DCommonUIComponents%2FLogos%5FRaw%2FATMOSPHERIC%2F%CE%912%2FNeanias%5FAtmosphere%5FAtmo%2DSEISM%2Epng&parent=%2Fteams%2Fh2020%2Dneanias%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP06%2DCoreServices%2FCore%20Services%2FC1%2DCommonUIComponents%2FLogos%5FRaw%2FATMOSPHERIC%2F%CE%912
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Application, Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Utilities, Workflows, Machine Learning, Image/data analysis
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research community, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Correlation, gas, radon, earthquake
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Alessandro
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Tibaldi
ERP.COI.3	Email	alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 3928633333
ERP.COI.5	Position	Ordinary Professor
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	University of Milan-Bicocca

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Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Alessandro
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Tibaldi
ERP.COI.9	Email	alessandro.tibaldi@unimib.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+39 3928633333
ERP.COI.11	Position	Ordinary Professor
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	University of Milan-Bicocca
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Bootstrap, Flask, Celery, Jinja2, Redis, uWSGI, nginx
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	18/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	First production release
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	None
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	None
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a2-2-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	

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Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Atmo-4CAST

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	atmo-4cast
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ATMO-4CAST
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Ubiwhere
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://atmo-4cast.neanias.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The ATMO-4CAST service allows the generation of meteorological forecasts, by using the Weather Forecast and Research Model. For this computation a user should provide relevant meteorological data for the forecast, an input example is provided. The results are downloadable files in different formats for a more custom analysis, and some PDF files with an initial graphical visualisation of the results.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Atmospheric Forecast
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://citegr.sharepoint.com/:i:/r/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/WP06-CoreServices/Core%20Services/C1-CommonUIComponents/Logos_Raw/ATMOSPHERIC/CE%913/Neanias_Atmosphere_Atmo-4CAST.png?csf=1&web=1&e=maBl4u
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis, Aggregators & Integrators
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Software & Data, Data Exploration, Image/data analysis
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research community, Research project, Research organization, Innovators, Business
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	

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Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Ricardo
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Vitorino
ERP.COI.3	Email	rvitorino@ubiwhere.com
ERP.COI.4	Phone	00351239151993
ERP.COI.5	Position	Head of Innovation
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Ubiwhere
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Ricardo
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Vitorino
ERP.COI.9	Email	rvitorino@ubiwhere.com
ERP.COI.10	Phone	00351239151993
ERP.COI.11	Position	Head of Innovation
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Ubiwhere
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	lcoimbra@ubiwhere.com
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	18/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission

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ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

3. Space sector

SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	INAF
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-vis.html
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The ViaLactea service provides an advanced operational solution for data management and visualization of astrophysics FAIR data surveys of the Galactic Plane to study the star formation process of the Milky Way. The ViaLactea Visual Analytic (VLVA) tool combines different types of visualization to perform the analysis exploring the correlation between different data, for example 2D intensity images with 3D molecular spectral cubes. All underlying data are managed in the ViaLactea Knowledge Base (VLKB). The VLKB includes 2D and 3D

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		(velocity cubes) surveys, numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues and allows for retrieval of all the available datasets as well as cutouts on the positional and/or velocity axis and some merging capabilities on adjacent datasets.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	SPACE-VIS ViaLactea Service for Galactic Plane data access and visualization under FAIR principles
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/images/logos/space-vis.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-vis.html
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Physical Sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Visualization
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Galactic Plane, Milky Way, Visualization, Visual Analytics, Virtual Observatory
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Marco
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Molinaro
ERP.COI.3	Email	marco.molinaro@inaf.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	INAF
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Eva
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Sciaccia
ERP.COI.9	Email	eva.sciaccia@inaf.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	

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ERP.COI.12	Organisation	INAF
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	helpdesk-neanias@inaf.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	security-neanias@inaf.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	IVOA
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

SPACE-VIS ADN Service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
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Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	SPACE-VIS ADN Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-vis.html
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	Astra Data Navigator (ADN) is a tool for 3D visualisation of stellar catalogues (stars, asteroids, planets, satellites, etc ...) in a navigable environment. The creation of the models takes place in real time based on the physical parameters read from the catalogues to try to make the representation as realistic as possible. In addition to reading the stellar catalogues, for bodies where it is possible, the placement in the environment is carried out through the use of Spice Kernels. ADN software have been tested on the Hipparcos and Tycho datasets and will be extended to use Gaia datasets.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Astrophysics Science
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Planetary Science
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Representation
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Software & Data
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Scientists, researchers, students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Client application
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Virtual Reality, Visualization, Virtual Observatory, GAIA, Universe Simulator
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy

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Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.3	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.9	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s1-service/en/latest/services/adn.html
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	

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ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

ADAM-SPACE

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ADAM (Advanced geospatial Data Management platform)
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	A major obstacle in Planetary data exploration is the technical steps involved in exploring the data. The goal of this service is to handle data and provide specific products of broad use (eg, mosaicking) as well as products that demand processing intensive tasks (eg, landing-sites). Make those products available publicly to ease access and allow users to reuse data.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Seamless access to planetary data
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Storage, Software, Data Management, Data Analysis, Education & Training, Network, Compute, Development Resource

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ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Data, File, Archive, Scientific/Research data, Data archives, Platform, Software, Access, Registration, Discovery, Maintenance
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research communities, Research Organisation, Students, Businesses
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Data Exploitation, Data Access, Data processing, data, datasets, data archive, celestial body, astrophysics, ICT data infrastructure, planetary science
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.3	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.5	Position	Managing Director
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Meteorological Enviromental Earth Observation
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.9	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.11	Position	Managing Director
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	

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ERP.MTI.4	Standards	OGC (WPS), OpenAPI
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Kubernetes, docker, Python, OIDC, Django
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/static/doc/ADAM_term_and_conditions.pdf
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/static/doc/ADAM_privacy_notice.pdf
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

ADAM-DPS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ADAM DPS - ADAM Data Processing System
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation

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ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://explorer-space.adamplatform.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The ADAM-DPS provides processing services to support the integration and management of data processing pipelines and job scheduling. S2.2 Data processing pipelines are integrated to support the exploitation of planetary science data. The main potential users are Astrophysics and Planetary scientists. Main potential stakeholders are Industries and agencies involved in Space missions and related technologies addressing space activities such as planetary mining engineering, planetary robotics, image processing, computer vision, mobile telecommunications and space weather.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Data Processing, Cloud Computing, Pipelines submission
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Management, Data Analysis, Compute
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Load Balancer, Virtual Machine Management, Container Management, Job Execution, Orchestration
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research communities, Research Organisation, Students, Businesses
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	data, datasets, data archive, data processing, cloud computing, job execution, pipeline, orchestration, AWS, STAC
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Austria (AT), Poland (PL), Germany (DE), United States of America (US)
Contact Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.3	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.9	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	OGC (WPS), OpenAPI
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Kubernetes, docker, Python, OIDC, Django, AWS
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

SPACE-ML CAESAR service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	SPACE-ML CAESAR service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica (INAF)
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	INAF
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-ml.html
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	CAESAR (Compact And Extended Sources Automated Recognition) service provides a straightforward solution to segment astrophysical FITS maps, allowing for the extraction and characterization of both compact (e.g. stars, galaxies) and extended sources (e.g. galactic filaments, supernovae remnants).
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	SPACE-ML CAESAR, an automated tool for source finding and characterization in astrophysical maps
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/images/logos/space-ml.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-ml.html
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Physical Sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Image/Data Analysis

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ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Astrophysics, Radio Astronomy, Source Finding, Source Extraction
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Riggi
ERP.COI.3	Email	simone.riggi@inaf.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	INAF
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Cristobal
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Bordiu
ERP.COI.9	Email	cristobal.bordiu@inaf.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	INAF
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	helpdesk-neanias@inaf.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	security-neanias@inaf.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		

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ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

SPACE-ML AstroML service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	SPACE-ML AstroML service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	INAF
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	INAF, UNIMIB, SZTAKI
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-ml.html
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	AstroML service has been developed for source identification, classification and characterization of sources in large-scale radio surveys. This includes a deep convolutional neural network based on an instance segmentation framework (R-CNN) that allows both detection and classification of radio compact sources, radio galaxies with extended morphology and sidelobe imaging artefacts. It can work either as a standalone source finder, or as a classifier stage

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		applied to source finders catalogue outputs of the CAESAR Service.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Machine Learning tool for source segmentation and classification in astrophysical maps
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/images/logos/space-ml.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://thematic.dev.neanias.eu/SPACE/space-ml.html
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Physical Sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Image/Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Astrophysics, Radio Astronomy, Source Finding, Source Extraction
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Filomena
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Bufano
ERP.COI.3	Email	filomena.bufano@inaf.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	INAF
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Carmelo
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Pino
ERP.COI.9	Email	carmelo.pino@inaf.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	INAF
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	helpdesk-neanias@inaf.it

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ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	security-neanias@inaf.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	AI-Gateway
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/s3-service/en/latest/services/ml.html
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

4. Core services

Catalogue Service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		

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ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Catalogue Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/openapi
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	NEANIAS Catalogue Service offers the API for external systems to programmatically manage and access the NEANIAS list of services and resources.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Neanias Resource catalogue: the NEANIAS gateway to EOSC
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/assets/images/NEANIAS.1ogo.NEW.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences, Environmental engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Aggregators & Integrators
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Services, Data, Software
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Providers, Research Managers, Business, Students, Policy Makers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Service Catalogue, EOSC
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WorldWide
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Greece, Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	George
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papastefanatos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapas@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	Senior Researcher
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	ATHENA Research Center

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Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	
ERP.COI.9	Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL-7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Postgres, Java EE, AngularJS
ERP.MTI.6	Version	v1.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	30/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	NEANIAS AAI
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The Framework Programme for research and Innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS Project (No.863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Fully Open Access

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ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

DVS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	DVS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	NKUA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://dvs.neanias.eu/v1.0/ui/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The Data Validation Service (DVS) allows users to rate (grade) the datasets they use and obtain the ratings of datasets. The identifier of a dataset is its DOI. It is accessible by other services via a REST API, allowing the calling services to create new dimensions for rating, to register ratings for datasets, and to obtain aggregate ratings for datasets.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Register and obtain dataset ratings
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://en.uoa.gr/fileadmin/user_upload/uoa_logo_eng.svg
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Development Resource, Measurement & Materials Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	APIs Repository/Gateway, Validation
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Reserach projects, Providers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Dataset rating
Geographical and Language Availability Information		

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ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Michalis
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Konstantopoulos
ERP.COI.3	Email	mkonstan@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Michalis
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Konstantopoulos
ERP.COI.9	Email	mkonstan@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	dvs_helpdesk@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	dvs_helpdesk@di.uoa.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	PostgreSQL, OpenAPI, Docker
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	22/09/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020

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ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/data-validation-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Catalogue Portal

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Catalogue Portal
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	ATHENA
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	NEANIAS Catalogue Portal is the main entry point for NEANIAS list of services and resources. End users, such as Researchers and Research Managers can browse and search the Catalogue for services related to their needs and select specific ones to view details about their characteristics. They can also compare services with similar ones of the same category and finally access and start using the service.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Neanias catalogue service: the NEANIAS facility for EOSC Exchange
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/assets/images/NEANIAS.1ogo.NEW.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	

D8.2 EOSC service model

Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Earth and related environmental sciences, Environmental engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Aggregators & Integrators
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Services, Data, Software
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Providers, Research Managers, Business, Students, Policy Makers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Service Catalogue, EOSC
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WorldWide
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Greece, Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	George
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papastefanatos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapas@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	Senior Researcher
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	ATHENA Research Center
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	
ERP.COI.9	Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	neanias_catalogue@athenarc.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL-7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	

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ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Postgres, Java EE, AngularJS
ERP.MTI.6	Version	v1.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	30/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	NEANIAS AAI
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The Framework Programme for research and Innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS Project (No.863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	http://catalogue.neanias.eu/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Fully Open Access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

NEANIAS AAI

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	NEANIAS AAI
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/aai-service/
Marketing Information		

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ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS AAI service offers a horizontal solution for all NEANIAS services to cover the common requirements of authenticated access, whether these come in the form of direct user requests or as cross service invocations. Furthermore, provisions to support some degree of the authorization of these requests is offered. The solution is based on widely accepted protocols and standards to ensure wide applicability of the approach.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Single Sign On, Authentication and Authorization
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	TBD
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Security & Identity
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Single Sign On, Identity and access management, User authentication
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	All
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Authentication, Authorization, Single-Sign-On, SSO, OpenID-Connect, SAML, User-Management, Roles, Permissions
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	OAuth2, OpenID Connect, SAML 2.0
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Keycloak
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/aai-service/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Configuration Service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Configuration Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/configuration-service
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS Configuration Management Service provides a key value storage for storing configurations that will be used by NEANIAS's services. Configurations are created or updated using dedicated client utilities
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Configuration Store
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Operations & Infrastructure Management Services
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Configuration
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Other
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Configuration
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios

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ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Zookeeper
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/configuration-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	

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ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Service Instance Registry

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Service Instance Registry
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/instance-registry-service
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS Service Instance Registry provides a list of all NEANIAS services among with information regarding their location and health status. NEANIAS's Services are registered dynamically, creating list of all available services and their instances. Service Discovery dedicated clients are available to provide real-time list of services, their location, and their health.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Service Instance Registry
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	TBD
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Operations & Infrastructure Management Services
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Utilities
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Other
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Service Instance, Discovery

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Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Zookeeper
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		

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ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/instance-registry-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Logging

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Log Aggregation
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/logging-service/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS Logging service provide an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can accumulate logs that are generated in a distributed fashion in a single centralized repository through well-defined endpoints and library utilities facilitating the transformation, enrichment and indexing of the log entries. The central repository can be searched and further aggregated to produce meaningful traces of user activity and facilitate troubleshooting and action auditing.

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ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Logging, Tracing, Analysis, Visualization, Log-Exporation
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	TBD
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Operations & Infrastructure Management Services
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Monitoring
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Resource Provider Managers, Resource Managers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Logging, Tracing
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		

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ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	ElasticSearch, Kibana, Logstash
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/logging-service/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Accounting

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Accounting

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ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/accounting-service
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS Accounting service provides an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can centrally log accounting information as it is gradually accumulated by their usage from the respective authorized clients. Different accumulation policies and granularity of information can be supported depending on the respective services. The information model consists of globally defined key point indicators and the aggregation and reports generated based on these will be available for further usage, as appropriate
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Accounting, Analysis, Visualization, Log-Exporation
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Operations & Infrastructure Management Services
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Accounting
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Research Organizations, Businesses, Resource Providers, Funders, Policy Members, Resource Managers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Accounting
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos

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ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	In Containment
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	ElasticSearch, Kibana, Logstash
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/accounting-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	

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ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Notifications

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Notification
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CITE
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/notification-service
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The NEANIAS Notification service acts as a generic notification provider for services that want to incorporate some sort of notification mechanism in their workflows. It allows generic configuration and parametrization of notification templates, give configuration options for selected notification channels to users and allow easy integration with other services that want to use its functionality.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Notification Handling
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	TBD
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Other
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Other
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Development Resource
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	APIs Repository / Gateway
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Other
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	free-conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Notification, Email
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	WW

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ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Greece (EL)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.3	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.5	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CITE
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Georgios
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Papanikos
ERP.COI.9	Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+302121020553
ERP.COI.11	Position	CTO
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CITE
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	gpapanikos@cite.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS

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Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/notification-service
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Data Depositing service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	GARR Cloud Platform Object Store
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	GARR
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/openstack/rclone_quick_tutorial/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The GARR Cloud Platform Object Store Service provides access to storage resources through an API. This allows a seamless and concurrent access to resources, which are in turn stored in redundant storage.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	RESTful storage
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://cloud.garr.it/static/GarrCloudWhite.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Generic
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Generic
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Storage
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Online
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Research organisations
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	object, store, storage, NREN

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Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Italy (IT)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Federico
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Ruggieri
ERP.COI.3	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 06 4962 2000
ERP.COI.5	Position	Director and coordinator
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Claudio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Pisa
ERP.COI.9	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Distributed Computing and Storage department
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	cloud-support@garr.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL8
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	ISO/IEC 27001:2013, ISO/IEC 27017:2015, ISO/IEC 27018:2019
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	Swift API
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Ceph, OpenStack
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service, GARR Container Platform Service, GARR DaaS
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	https://cloud.garr.it

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ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/privacy/
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	https://www.garr.it/en/network-access-rules
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Data Sharing

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	DaShaS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	NKUA
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://files.neanias.eu
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The Data Sharing Service (DaShaS) is a service used by the NEANIAS thematic services (and via them, by their end-users) to allow data stored internally to be shared between the end users and thematic services. For example, a user of a thematic service can provide input to a thematic service and then get the output of the calculation via DaShaS.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Store datasets, share with thematic services and get back services' output
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://en.uoa.gr/fileadmin/user_upload/uoa_logo_eng.svg
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Storage, Data, Application

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ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Data, File, Online, Synchronised, Online service data
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Research projects, Providers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Store, Share
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Michalis
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Konstantopoulos
ERP.COI.3	Email	mkonstan@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Michalis
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Konstantopoulos
ERP.COI.9	Email	mkonstan@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	dashas_helpdesk@di.uoa.gr
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	dashas_helpdesk@di.uoa.gr
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL9
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Nextcloud
ERP.MTI.6	Version	19.0.3
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	

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Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

Data Exploration

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	ADAM (Advanced geospatial Data Management platform)
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://explorer.adamplatform.eu/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	ADAM: The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data. ADAM allows you extracting global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and

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		long-term projections. Most of the data are updated daily to allow users having always the most recent data to play with.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Seamless access to geospatial data
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqy-bd6CpXMOIRqfHmBqIzW/featured , https://www.meeo.it/application-areas/
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Storage, Software, Data Management, Data Analysis, Education & Training, Network, Compute, Development Resource
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Load Balancer, Virtual Machine Management, Container Management, , Job Execution, Orchestration, Data, File, Archive, Scientific/Research data, Data archives, Platform, Software, Access, Registration, Discovery, Maintenance
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research communities, Research Organisation, Students, Businesses
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free, Free-conditionally, Paid
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Data Exploitation, Data Access, Data processing, data, datasets, data archive, Air quality, agriculture, climate change, cultural heritage, coastal and marine environment, forestry, natural disaster, ICT data infrastructure, planetary science, RDA, AWS Open Data Registry, OGC, STAC
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Austria (AT), Poland (PL), Germany (DE), United States of America (US)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.3	Email	mantovani@meeo.it

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ERP.COI.4	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.5	Position	Managing Director
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Simone
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Mantovani
ERP.COI.9	Email	mantovani@meeo.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	05321861501
ERP.COI.11	Position	Managing Director
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Meteorological Environmental Earth Observation
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	contactus@adamplatform.eu
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL8
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	OGC services (OpenSearch, WMS, WCS, WPS), OpenAPI backends
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Kubernetes, docker, Python, OIDC, Django
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	contactus@adamplatform.eu
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	https://explorer.adamplatform.eu/static/doc/ADAM_term_and_conditions.pdf
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://explorer.adamplatform.eu/static/doc/ADAM_privacy_notice.pdf
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	

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ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqy-bd6CpXMOIRqfHmBqLZw/featured
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

GARR Cloud Platform Service

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	GARR Cloud Platform Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	GARR
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://cloud.garr.it/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The GARR Cloud Platform Service allows to use a set of computational, networking and storage resources to create services based on virtual machines. It's operational model is federated, open and reproducible. This allows organisations either to avoid managing their resources at their premises, or to join the GARR Cloud federation using their hardware resources or to reproduce the GARR Cloud model at their premises.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	The flexible and open cloud for researchers
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://cloud.garr.it/_static/GarrCloudWhite.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://cloud.garr.it/doc/videos/
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Generic
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Generic
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Compute
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Virtual Machine Management
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Research organisations
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	

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ERP.CLI.8	Tags	OpenStack, IaaS, Virtual Machines, NREN
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Italy (IT)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Federico
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Ruggieri
ERP.COI.3	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 06 4962 2000
ERP.COI.5	Position	Director and coordinator
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Claudio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Pisa
ERP.COI.9	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Distributed Computing and Storage department
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	cloud-support@garr.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL8
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	ISO/IEC 27001:2013, ISO/IEC 27017:2015, ISO/IEC 27018:2019
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Ceph, OpenStack, Juju
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Object Store, GARR Container Platform Service, GARR DaaS

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ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	https://cloud.garr.it
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://cloud.garr.it/doc/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/privacy/
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	https://www.garr.it/en/network-access-rules
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	https://cloud.garr.it/doc/tutorials/
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

GARR Container Platform

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	GARR Container Platform Service
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	GARR
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://cloud.garr.it/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The GARR Container Platform, based on Kubernetes, allows the orchestration of CPU and GPU based containers to support a wide range of research oriented applications.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Kubernetes for researchers
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://cloud.garr.it/_static/GarrCloudWhite.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	-
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Generic

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ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Generic
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Compute
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Container Management
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Research organisations
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Kubernetes, PaaS, Containers, NREN
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Italy (IT)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Federico
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Ruggieri
ERP.COI.3	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 06 4962 2000
ERP.COI.5	Position	Director and coordinator
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Claudio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Pisa
ERP.COI.9	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Distributed Computing and Storage department
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	cloud-support@garr.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL8
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	ISO/IEC 27001:2013, ISO/IEC 27017:2015, ISO/IEC 27018:2019
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Kubernetes, Ceph, OpenStack, Juju

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ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service, GARR DaaS
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service, GARR Cloud Platform Object Store, GARR DaaS
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	https://cloud.garr.it
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://cloud.garr.it/containers/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/privacy/
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	https://www.garr.it/en/network-access-rules
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	https://cloud.garr.it/containers/
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

GARR DaaS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	GARR DaaS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	GARR
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://cloud.garr.it/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	GARR DaaS (Deployment as a Service) allows users to deploy and orchestrate a wide range of applications on top of the GARR Cloud Platform Service. Tools for

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		Data processing, such as Apache Spark, Hadoop and ElasticSearch can be deployed through a web interface. A complete list of supported applications can be found at https://jaas.ai
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Deployment as a Service
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://cloud.garr.it/_static/GarrCloudWhite.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	-
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Generic
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Generic
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Compute
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Orchestration
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Research organisations
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	applications, deployment, orchestration, NREN
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Italy (IT)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Federico
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Ruggieri
ERP.COI.3	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+39 06 4962 2000
ERP.COI.5	Position	Director and coordinator
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Claudio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Pisa
ERP.COI.9	Email	cloud-support@garr.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Distributed Computing and Storage department
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	Consortium GARR
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	cloud-support@garr.it

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ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	cloud-support@garr.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	ISO/IEC 27001:2013, ISO/IEC 27017:2015, ISO/IEC 27018:2019
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Kubernetes, Ceph, OpenStack, Juju
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	GARR Cloud Platform Service, GARR Cloud Platform Object Store, GARR Cloud Container Platform Service
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	https://cloud.garr.it
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://cloud.garr.it/apps/
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	https://cloud.garr.it/terms/privacy/
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	https://www.garr.it/en/network-access-rules
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

C3.1-AI-Gateway

Code	Attribute Name	Value
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Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	AI-Gateway
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	SZTAKI
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-1-ai-gateway/en/latest/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	A web-based development environment for scientists to design, develop and evaluate machine learning solutions. The core technology is Python, which is the most popular programming language in machine learning and data science scenes. Jupyter Hub is a multi-user development environment using the IPython interface, allowing code implementation and interpretation using a web interface. The kernel used includes TensorFlow and Keras (www.keras.io), as the most popular libraries for neural network development, and other relevant packages as well.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Service for Development of Machine Learning Model using Jupyter Hub.
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://www.sztaki.hu/sites/default/files/2019/page/media/logo_2019_1.zip
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	-
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	-
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Machine Learning
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)

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Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	József
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Kovács
ERP.COI.3	Email	jozsef.kovacs@sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+36 1 279 6066
ERP.COI.5	Position	senior research fellow
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	SZTAKI
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	József
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Kovács
ERP.COI.9	Email	jozsef.kovacs@sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+36 1 279 6066
ERP.COI.11	Position	senior research fellow
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	SZTAKI
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	neanias@lists.lpds.sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	neanias@lists.lpds.sztaki.hu
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL8
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Jupyter, Python
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	NEANIAS AAI
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	

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ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

C3.3-Horovod-Cluster

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	Horovod cluster
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	SZTAKI
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-3-horovod/en/latest/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The training of deep neural networks on big data takes significant time, even on GPU-enabled workstations. To increase efficiency, a distributed computation cluster should be used, where users can define models to train and collect results. This service is a horovod based architecture of GPU-accelerated nodes, where the communication is based on the MPI protocol. The training jobs are queued, resulting in model parameters, and training logs are served to the user. Real-time tracking of the training process is possible, e.g. using TensorBoard.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Distributed training of large ML models using Horovod
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://www.sztaki.hu/sites/default/files/2019/page/media/logo_2019_1.zip
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences

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ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Machine Learning
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free conditionally
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Attila
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Farkas
ERP.COI.3	Email	attila.farkas@sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+36 1 279 6067
ERP.COI.5	Position	research associate
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	SZTAKI
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Attila
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Farkas
ERP.COI.9	Email	attila.farkas@sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+36 1 279 6067
ERP.COI.11	Position	research associate
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	SZTAKI
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	neanias@lists.lpds.sztaki.hu
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	neanias@lists.lpds.sztaki.hu
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Implementation
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Open access
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

C3.4-Spark-Cluster

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.BAI.1	Name	Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-4-spark/en/latest/
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The service represents a Spark based solution for distributed training and execution of ML tasks. The service currently takes the form of a Jupyter Notebook, supporting a range of functionalities offered by the Spark ML APIs for Python.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Distributed machine learning on a Kubernetes based Spark distribution, with Jupyterhub integration
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://gvizzari.hopto.org/imgdepot/logo-c34.png
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Development Resource, Compute
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	APIs Repository/Gateway, Job Execution, Orchestration
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research group, Research community, Students, Innovators, Businesses, Providers, Policy Makers, Research Infrastructure Managers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Virtual
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Spark, Distributed computing, Jupyter, AI, ML, clustering
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Europe
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Thomas
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Cecconello
ERP.COI.3	Email	thomas.cecconello@unimib.it

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ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	UNIMIB
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Giuseppe
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Vizzari
ERP.COI.9	Email	giuseppe.vizzari@unimib.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	UNIMIB
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Apache Spark, Kubernetes
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission (EC)
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	The framework programme for research and innovation (H2020)
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS project under grant No. 863448
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	

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ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Request/Order required
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

VD-VisIVO

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	VD-VisIVO
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	INAF
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	INAF
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vd.html#vd-visivo
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The service offers a framework for data intensive visual discovery for experiments and data analysis (including support for training of researchers and public outreach). The service makes available for data processing and visual discovery the suite of tools provided by VisIVO. VisIVO is specifically designed for distributed computing environments such as cloud infrastructures and offers a framework for exploration of large-scale scientific data-sets creating customized views of 3D renderings from multi-dimensional data tables from various sources.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Scientific visualization of multidimensional data
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	https://github.com/inaf-oact-VisIVO/VisIVOserver/blob/master/visivo-logo.png?raw=true
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	https://youtu.be/f_R6W-mm4c0
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences,
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Physical Sciences,
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Visualization

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ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Researchers, Research Groups, Students
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Visualization, Virtual Observatory
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	EN
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Fabio
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Vitello
ERP.COI.3	Email	fabio.vitello@inaf.it
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	INAF
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Fabio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Vitello
ERP.COI.9	Email	fabio.vitello@inaf.it
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	INAF
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	helpdesk-neanias@inaf.it
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	security-neanias@inaf.it
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL 7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Operational
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	IVOA
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	1.0.0
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	Visualization Gateway
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vd.html#vd-visivo
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

VD-MAPS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	VD-MAPS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	CORONIS
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	CORONIS
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	https://vd-maps.neanias.eu
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	VD-Maps service deals with the creation of tiled web maps for visualization on Cesium JS of both 2D and 2.5D datasets.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	Visualization on Cesium JS
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	No logo available for core services
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	-

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ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Natural Sciences, Engineering & Technology, Humanities
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Computer and information sciences, Earth and related environmental sciences, Biological sciences, Electrical, electronic and information engineering, Environmental engineering, Environmental biotechnology, History and archaeology
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Visualization
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Individual Researchers, Research Groups, Research community, Reserach projects, Innovators, Scientists, Businesses, SMEs
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	Remote
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	Free
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	Underwater Mapping Service
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	Worldwide (WW)
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English (en)
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy (IT), Spain (ES)
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Ricard
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Campos
ERP.COI.3	Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.4	Phone	+34 972 18 32 41
ERP.COI.5	Position	Research & Development Engineer
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	CORONIS
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Ricard
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Campos
ERP.COI.9	Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.10	Phone	+34 972 18 32 41
ERP.COI.11	Position	Research & Development Engineer
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	CORONIS
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	ricard.campos@coroni.es

D8.2 EOSC service model

Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL7
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	Production
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	Bootstrap, Flask, Celery, Jinja2, Redis, uWSGI, nginx, opencv, openmvg, openmvs, cesium
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	15/11/2020
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	European Commission
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	Horizon 2020
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	NEANIAS (863448)
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/software/vd.html#vd-maps-software
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	Free (requires authentication)
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

C4.3- Toolkit for Cross Realities – PMS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR) PMS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR, ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	<p>The service is a web-server developed in Python that offers a series of RESTful APIs for the simplified and optimized use of SPICE through the use of the Python wrapper of the Spice toolkits.</p> <p>This service can be deployed on the cloud allowing for scalability.</p> <p>The current version can be released as a Docker container.</p> <p>The PMS needs at least one Meta Kernel containing one or more Spice Kernels, loaded through configuration.</p>
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Astrophysics Science
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Planetary Science
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Web Service & Data
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Scientists, researchers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	
ERP.CLI.8	Tags	
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		

D8.2 EOSC service model

Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.3	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.9	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	TRL6
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		
ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	

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ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	

C4.3- Toolkit for Cross Realities – DCS

Code	Attribute Name	Value
Basic Information		
ERP.BAI.0	ID	
ERP.BAI.1	Name	C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR) DCS
ERP.BAI.2	Resource Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.3	Resource Providers	GARR, ALTEC S.p.A
ERP.BAI.4	Webpage	
Marketing Information		
ERP.MRI.1	Description	The service is a web-server developed in Python that offers a possibility to query different datastore through the use of metadata. This service can be deployed on the cloud allowing for scalability. The current version can be released as a Docker container. The DCS requires the configuration for access to the various data stores during the deployment phase.
ERP.MRI.2	Tagline	
ERP.MRI.3	Logo	
ERP.MRI.4	Multimedia	
ERP.MRI.5	Use Cases	
Classification Information		
ERP.CLI.1	Scientific Domain	Astrophysics Science
ERP.CLI.2	Scientific Subdomain	Planetary Science
ERP.CLI.3	Category	Data Analysis
ERP.CLI.4	Subcategory	Web Service & Data
ERP.CLI.5	Target Users	Scientists, researchers
ERP.CLI.6	Access Type	
ERP.CLI.7	Access Mode	

D8.2 EOSC service model

ERP.CLI.8	Tags	
Geographical and Language Availability Information		
ERP.GLA.1	Geographical Availability	World
ERP.GLA.2	Language Availability	English
Resource Location Information		
ERP.RLI.01	Resource Geographic Location	Italy
Contact Information		
Main Contact/Resource Owner		
ERP.COI.1	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.2	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.3	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.4	Phone	
ERP.COI.5	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.6	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Public Contact		
ERP.COI.7	First Name	Eugenio
ERP.COI.8	Last Name	Topa
ERP.COI.9	Email	eugenio.topa@altec.space
ERP.COI.10	Phone	
ERP.COI.11	Position	Coordinator, Developer
ERP.COI.12	Organisation	ALTEC S.p.A
Other Contacts		
ERP.COI.13	Helpdesk Email	
ERP.COI.14	Security Contact Email	
Maturity Information		
ERP.MTI.1	Technology Readiness Level	
ERP.MTI.2	Life Cycle Status	
ERP.MTI.3	Certifications	
ERP.MTI.4	Standards	
ERP.MTI.5	Open Source Technologies	
ERP.MTI.6	Version	
ERP.MTI.7	Last Update	
ERP.MTI.8	Change Log	
Dependencies Information		
ERP.DEI.1	Required Resources	
ERP.DEI.2	Related Resources	
ERP.DEI.3	Related Platforms	
Attribution Information		

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ERP.ATI.1	Funding Body	
ERP.ATI.2	Funding Program	
ERP.ATI.3	Grant/Project Name	
Management Information		
ERP.MGI.1	Helpdesk Page	
ERP.MGI.2	User Manual	
ERP.MGI.3	Terms Of Use	
ERP.MGI.4	Privacy Policy	
ERP.MGI.5	Access Policy	
ERP.MGI.6	Service Level	
ERP.MGI.7	Training Information	
ERP.MGI.8	Status Monitoring	
ERP.MGI.9	Maintenance	
Access and Order Information		
ERP.AOI.1	Order Type	
ERP.AOI.2	Order	
Financial Information		
ERP.FNI.1	Payment Model	
ERP.FNI.2	Pricing	